

Irregular migration from France to Great Britain in small boats: highlighting female experiences and perspectives

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***Irregular migration from France to Great Britain in small boats:
highlighting female experiences and perspectives***

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Acronyms:

GCM	Global Compact on Migration
GCR	Global Compact on Refugees
IOM	International Organization for Migration
LGBTQI+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and intersexed+
NGO	Non-Government Organization
OHCHR	Office of the UN High Commissioner of Human Rights
(S)GBV	(Sexual and) Gender Based Violence
UKHoCHAC	UK House of Commons Home Affairs Committee
UNHCR	UN High Commissioner for Refugees

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Summary

- Irregular migration using small boats from France to the UK, in 2022 accounting for approximately half of all undocumented migrant entries, has grown dramatically over the last four years, and continues to grow. It is a dynamic and evolving situation, both in terms of the profiles of migrants but also in terms of the non-stop whirl of commentary and fulmination from all sides.
- This dissertation presents and analyzes the situation and history from the two sides of the Channel, and within this context provides detailed examples and case studies of female experiences and perspectives.
- Migrants have tried to cross the Channel irregularly since the 1990s and the popularity of small boats has increased as it has become harder to use other routes (such as on the back of trucks or by Eurotunnel).
- There are clear push and pull factors for migrants. Important among these is that conditions in northern France are particularly hostile, including a more complex and undesirable process for claiming asylum than the UK.
- While women and girls make up approximately 10% of Channel crossings, they have particular vulnerabilities, particularly in terms of sexual and other forms of violence and in terms of health.
- Media and public discourse around the situation tends to be either gender-blind or contain stereotypes. In terms of operational responses, some are gender-sensitive, although entrenched structural barriers get in the way of anything that is truly gender-responsive.
- British and French efforts to address the situation are hampered by polarized thinking and inadequate communication on many levels. Improving joint understanding and exchanges, with a better appreciation of the positions of all stakeholders involved, is proposed as the best way forward. Any solution will be imperfect, but a more effectively planned and managed approach would help to better satisfy national interests while reducing danger, terrible conditions and misery for migrants.
- This dissertation may provide lessons for other seemingly intractable situations involving irregular migration. There is every indication that this will increase in the future.

Résumé (français)

- La migration irrégulière par petits bateaux de la France vers le Royaume-Uni, qui représente en 2022 environ la moitié de toutes les entrées de migrants sans papiers, a connu une croissance spectaculaire au cours des quatre dernières années, et continue de croître. Il s'agit d'une situation dynamique et évolutive, à la fois en termes de profils de migrants mais aussi en termes de tourbillon non-stop de commentaires et de fulminations de toutes parts.
- La thèse présente et analyse la situation et l'histoire des deux côtés de la Manche, et dans ce contexte, fournit des exemples détaillés et des études de cas d'expériences et de perspectives féminines.
- Les migrants tentent de traverser la Manche d'une manière irrégulière depuis les années 1990 et la popularité des petits bateaux a augmenté car il est devenu plus difficile d'utiliser d'autres itinéraires (comme à l'arrière des camions ou par l'Eurotunnel).
- Il existe des facteurs d'attraction et de répulsion évidents pour les migrants. L'un des plus importants est que les conditions dans le nord de la France sont particulièrement hostiles, avec notamment une procédure de demande d'asile plus complexe et moins souhaitable qu'au Royaume-Uni.
- Alors que les femmes et les filles représentent environ 10% des traversées de la Manche, elles sont particulièrement vulnérables, notamment en termes de santé et de violences sexuelles et autres.
- Les médias et le discours public sur la situation ont tendance à ne pas tenir compte du genre ou à contenir des stéréotypes. En termes de réponses opérationnelles, certaines sont sensibles au genre, bien que des barrières structurelles bien ancrées fassent obstacle à tout ce qui est réellement sensible au genre.
- Les efforts britanniques et français pour s'attaquer à la situation sont entravés par une pensée polarisée et une communication inadéquate à de nombreux niveaux. La meilleure façon d'aller de l'avant est d'améliorer la compréhension mutuelle et les échanges, avec une meilleure appréciation des positions de tous les acteurs impliqués. Toute solution sera imparfaite, mais une approche plus efficacement planifiée et gérée permettrait de mieux satisfaire les intérêts nationaux tout en réduisant le danger, les conditions terribles et la misère des migrants.
- Cette thèse peut fournir des leçons pour d'autres situations apparemment insolubles impliquant la migration irrégulière. Tout porte à croire que ce phénomène va s'amplifier à l'avenir.

Resumen (español)

- La migración irregular en embarcaciones precarias desde Francia al Reino Unido, que en 2022 representa aproximadamente la mitad de todas las entradas de inmigrantes indocumentados, ha crecido de forma espectacular en los últimos cuatro años, y sigue aumentando. Se trata de una situación dinámica y en evolución, tanto por el perfil de los migrantes como por el torbellino incesante de comentarios y fulminaciones de todas las partes.
- La disertación presenta y analiza la situación y la historia desde ambos lados del Canal de la Mancha, y dentro de este contexto ofrece ejemplos detallados y estudios de casos de experiencias y perspectivas femeninas.
- Desde la década de 1990 los inmigrantes han intentado cruzar el Canal de manera irregular y la popularidad de las embarcaciones precarias ha aumentado a medida que se ha hecho más difícil utilizar otras rutas (como en la parte trasera de los camiones o por el Eurotúnel).
- Existen claros factores de empuje y atracción para los emigrantes. Uno de ellos es que las condiciones en el norte de Francia son especialmente hostiles, ya que el proceso de solicitud de asilo es más complejo e indeseable que en el Reino Unido.
- Las mujeres y las niñas representan aproximadamente el 10% de las personas que cruzan el Canal y son especialmente vulnerables, víctimas de todo tipo de violencia.
- Los medios de comunicación y el discurso público tienden a ignorar el género de las personas migrantes o a tener estereotipos. En cuanto a las respuestas operativas, algunas sí tienen en cuenta la perspectiva de género, a pesar de las arraigadas barreras estructurales que existen.
- Los esfuerzos británicos y franceses por abordar la situación se ven obstaculizados por un pensamiento polarizado y una comunicación inadecuada en muchos niveles. La manera de avanzar es mejorar el entendimiento y los intercambios conjuntos, con una apreciación de las posiciones de todas las partes implicadas. Cualquier solución será imperfecta, pero un planteamiento más eficazmente planificado y gestionado ayudaría a satisfacer mejor los intereses nacionales, reduciendo al mismo tiempo el peligro, las terribles condiciones y la miseria de los inmigrantes.
- La disertación puede aportar enseñanzas para otras situaciones aparentemente irresolubles relacionadas con la migración irregular. Todo indica que ésta aumentará en el futuro.

Chapter 1. Introduction, process and objectives

An annual cross-border flow of 28,000 in 2021, compared to an estimate of 281 million international migrants in the world 2020 (IOM, 2021 December), might seem relatively insignificant.

However the rapid growth of irregular migrants (see definitions in Box 1) crossing the English Channel (*La Manche* for the French) in small boats¹ over the last four years has generated an inordinate amount of attention. Boat passages carry high risks². Circumstances are fast-moving and new material and reports are available almost daily. There is consequently a rich and diverse range of material and research available³⁴.

Structure of dissertation

This Chapter provides some key definitions, rationale and context for undertaking the research. Chapter 2 sets out relevant background. Chapter 3 then summarizes some of the normative frameworks, principally from the UN, and theoretical frameworks which guided the research. Chapter 4 considers developments and different general perspectives in the last four years in terms of (arriving in) the UK and (leaving and living in) France, concluding with a consideration of cultural differences between the two countries.

In the second part of the dissertation, Chapter 5 unpacks different elements of a gender lens, with reference to practical frameworks, before considering how stereotypes shape understanding and discourse around migration and gender. Chapter 6 builds on the previous chapters and collates experiences of women and girl Channel migrants, reflecting on why there is a limited proportion of female migrants and then grouping areas including sexual violence; health; water, food, shelter and education; border crossings; and state assistance (or lack of it).

¹ Referred to as 'Channel crossings' in the dissertation

² "due to the dense shipping traffic ... strong currents, frequent fog and low water temperatures. This is especially true when people resort to unsuitable boats, children's inflatable boats, self-constructions from surfboards or attempts to swim." (Müller, 2021)

³ While responding to queries requesting information, Care4Calais and Women for Refuges both indicated they received many requests to support research and were unable to help. The Calais sous-préfecture did not respond to a request for information despite a visit and a follow-up email.

⁴ The Migration Observatory (2021, July 2) provides one of the best snapshots of the issue

Box 1: Defining migrants, irregular migration and refugees

'Migrant', used in this dissertation, encompasses a diverse range of people as noted by Human Rights Watch (2021):

"The term 'migrant' is not defined in international law; our use of this term is in its 'common lay understanding of a person who moves away from his or her place of usual residence, whether within a country or across an international border, temporarily or permanently, and for a variety of reasons.' It includes asylum seekers and refugees ... Some groups in France, including the French Defender of Rights, use the term 'exile' in preference to 'migrant.'⁵

The International Organization for Migration (IOM) defines irregular migration as follows:

"Movement of persons that takes place outside the laws, regulations, or international agreements governing the entry into or exit from the State of origin, transit or destination."

The UN High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)⁶ defines refugees as:

"people who have fled war, violence, conflict or persecution and have crossed an international border to find safety in another country ... [who] are defined and protected in international law, ... [citing the] 1951 Refugee Convention, 'someone who is unable or unwilling to return to their country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion.'"

⁵ For a deconstruction of the term, see Leprince (2020)

⁶ <https://www.unhcr.org/what-is-a-refugee.html>

My conclusion ends with a recommendation, followed by a list of references and several annexes, including collated case studies on female migrants and details on female deaths on the border.

As a British citizen who also acquired French nationality in 2019, I have followed coverage around irregular migration into Europe with interest and concern, noting considerably divergent opinions related to immigration. These are exemplified when comparing books such as Yeo's (2020) plea for a more humane British immigration system seeing asylum seekers as potential "citizens-in-waiting" and Murray's (2017) critique of what he sees as overly and naive acceptance of massive unregulated immigration into Europe since 2015 which has meant the continent and "its leaders have decided to commit suicide".

My research was almost entirely desk-based, undertaken between April–August 2022, with a visit to the *Calaisis*⁷ between 18–21 July that incorporated one day of volunteering with the NGO *Salam* that provided lunch to around 120 migrants. Marie, the volunteer who was coordinating that day, wrote that she had been volunteering for 15 years and nothing had changed for migrants, indeed conditions were even more miserable⁸.

While a broad range of perspectives were considered, the research inevitably focuses more on areas where information was easily available, so for example there is more detail on conditions facing migrants in France (with much about the 'Calais Jungle' camp that gained notoriety before the increase in small boat Channel crossings) than in the UK, and more on UK than French public opinion.

I undertook research in both English and French, which allowed me to more easily review different national perspectives. My approach has also been informed by having nearly 25 years' experience in international and non-government organizations.

The dissertation principally considers the second of three different stages of migration (Boyd and Grieco, 2003), *the transition across state boundaries*⁹, conscious that it is important to be

⁷ The region around Calais and loosely used in the report to indicate the area in northern France from which migrants leave the country.

⁸ "Je suis à Salam depuis 15 ans et rien n'a changé, c'est encore plus misérable"

⁹ From Boyd and Grieco (2003), "There are three distinct stages where gender relations, roles, and hierarchies influence the migration process and produce differential outcomes for women: the pre-

aware of multiple dimensions from places of departure to those of reception, including longer-term historical factors¹⁰. It focuses on female perspectives around Channel crossings, although many of the observations and analyses (particularly in the first part) apply to all migrants. By focusing on women and girls, even though they represent around 1 in 10 of Channel migrants, the dissertation also provides generic insights on gender around irregular migration. While references to women and girls were somewhat limited in documents (many sources are gender-blind), the research found that there were considerably more details available about the experience of children, which is largely outside the scope of the dissertation.

The Channel crossings fit into a broader historical situation of irregular crossings which dates back to 1990 with the opening of the Channel Tunnel. There are also important historical landmarks in terms of the UK Brexit vote on 23 June 2016 (influenced by immigration and with the backdrop of massive immigration into Europe, particularly from Syria) and subsequent UK withdrawal from the European Union (EU) on 31 December 2020.

With rising inequalities and other factors such as climate change and war, irregular migration is only likely to increase across the world in the future. Undocumented population movements, and the variable state responses and polarized popular sentiment they generate, both expose the fragility of international migration and refugee law as well as providing a touchstone of the impact upon receiving societies.

Overall, this dissertation argues that the state response to the Channel crossings in France and the UK, and communication between the two countries, leave much to be desired. There are examples of bad practice, downright if not deliberate neglect, and political profiteering. It is hoped that the information and analysis will inform and improve policy-making and practice, in the region and for other borders involving irregular migration.

migration stage, the transition across state boundaries, and the experiences of migrants in the receiving country.”

¹⁰ The main perspective of the dissertation is from the countries of reception (the UK and France), notwithstanding the complexity of issues related to countries of departure, with push factors that can be traced back to, for example, wars in Afghanistan (2001-2021), Iraq (2003-2011), Libya (2011) and colonial history.

Chapter 2. Background, history and political situation

Broader migration questions and perceptions in the UK

Migration has existed since the beginning of human history, and has been particularly associated with wars, natural disasters and population pressure.

Massive movements of population took place between the 16th and 20th centuries out of Europe, including approximately 15 million people alone migrating from the UK between 1850–1914, principally to Australia and New Zealand. Since then Europe has also seen large movements during and after the Second World War, between that time and the 1980s with workers emigrating to northern Europe, as a consequence of the Balkans wars, and more recently during the Ukraine war.

In the UK¹¹, under the New Labour government, net migration quadrupled from around 50,000 every year before 1997 to an average of 200,000 each year between 1997–2010.

“During this period around 2.2 million immigrants entered the United Kingdom, the salience of the issue of immigration rose to one of the most prominent political issues in the country, and the impact of the net increase has changed the ethnic demography of the United Kingdom.”¹²

Growth in immigration from the accession of the ‘A8 countries’¹³ in the EU was accompanied by a clear change in public mood from 2001–2016, with immigration rising as a primary concern between 2001 and 2016.

¹¹ See UK Office for National Statistics (2021) on the complexity of measuring migration in the country

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Immigration_under_New_Labour_from_1997_-_2010

¹³ A8 countries were previously the Eastern Bloc in Europe: Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia

Annex 1 contains charts showing UK public opinion on immigration. UK voter judgements on immigration¹⁴, personal economic circumstances, and ‘taking back control’ were shown to be particularly significant factors in the 2016 Brexit vote (Parker, 2018)¹⁵. Since 2015 the salience of immigration has fallen from 1st to 9th place in terms of ‘the most/other important issues facing Britain today’), and in the last two years returning to what was the last previous low level in 1999. However when questioned about Channel crossings, 67% of respondents agreed with statements against immigration compared with 45% supporting immigration. 52% of people felt the government was ‘not doing enough to stop channel migrant crossing’¹⁶. Conversely, with responses relatively constant over the last three years, 56% of people had ‘a great deal’ or ‘fair amount’ of sympathy for these migrants (IPSOS, 2022; The Migrant Observatory, 2020)¹⁷. The British Refugee Council (2022) suggests:

“The government has repeatedly referred to people crossing the Channel in small boats as ‘economic¹⁸ migrants’ rather than people ‘in genuine need of protection’ and have created a narrative suggesting that these people are somehow ‘jumping the queue’ in front of others in need of protection.”

Citing Chimini’s (1998) idea of ‘myth of difference’, Ramasubramanyam (2022) suggests that thinking about refugees can be skewed and selective, stemming from the fact that the 1951 Refugee Convention focused on Europe while the 1967 protocol expanded this for a universal application of the Convention’s norms.

Considering UK emigration, Jerrim (2015) estimated 4.7 million British nationals lived abroad¹⁹.

¹⁴ Parker (2018) remarks, for “many of those most opposed to migration, their views had not been formed with reference to any direct experience of migrants or of the effects of migration (and, indeed, many with direct experience voted Remain).”

¹⁵ See video showing continued right-wing backlash to immigration from Channel crossings in PBS News Hour (2020)

¹⁶ Kirk (2021) presents a YouGov survey which suggested 82% of Britons found that the “government is handling the issue of Channel crossings by asylum seekers badly”.

¹⁷ See Wright (2022) on how the community in Dover views the crossings

¹⁸ The Macmillan Dictionary (<https://www.macmillandictionary.com/dictionary/british/economic-migrant0>) defines an economic migrant as “someone who goes to a new country because living conditions or opportunities for jobs are not good in their own country. This word is used by governments to show that a person is not considered a refugee.”

¹⁹ Without entering into a discussion on open borders (e.g. see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_border) many have questioned how definitions of ‘regular’ and ‘irregular’ migration can be considered artificial, or at the least underline issues of injustice and inequality.

Comparing numbers of asylum applications in Europe

Figure 1 suggests that in total and proportionally per capita, the UK has received fewer asylum applications between 2014–2020, even though many would argue that it has received its “fair share”.

Figure 1 - ‘The UK has received far fewer asylum applications than most EU countries’

Source: Gross and Wright (2021)

Recent history of irregular migration over and under the Channel

Agrier and Courant (2022) consider that irregular migration started increasing from France to the UK since around 1990, and especially after the opening of the Channel Tunnel in 1994, with subsequent Anglo–French agreements such as the Sangatte (1993)²⁰ and Le Touquet (2004)²¹ protocols and the Sandhurst communiqué (2018)²² providing a framework for ‘juxtaposed’ controls²³.

In relation to Channel migrations, the Sandhurst communiqué:

- reaffirms the two countries working “closely together at all levels to reduce migrant pressures and target criminal gangs involved in people trafficking, both in northern France and further afield”;
- seeks to “address the shared challenges posed by illegal migration, “modern slavery”, and human trafficking and to support regular and well-managed legal migration flows”; and
- indicates the UK “shall support France in its provision of accommodation in facilities located outside the Calais and Dunkirk areas, such as Reception and Assessment Centres” and will provide an [initial] “package of cooperation including €50m additional United Kingdom financial support for 2018”.

After the juxtaposed UK border was displaced to France, security measures have been increasingly tightened, subject to (video) surveillance and ‘fortified’ (Agrier and Courant, 2022) with mounting deaths of migrants²⁴ attempting to cross the Channel (Institute of Race Relations,

²⁰

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/273137/2366.pdf

²¹ <http://www.fortunes-de-mer.com/mer/images/documents%20pdf/legislation/Internationale/Surete/Traite%20Touquet%202003%20ORU.pdf> ; see also analysis by The Local (2022, April 15)

²²

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/674880/2018_UK-FR_Summit_Communique.pdf

²³ Establishing and maintaining French immigration staff in British ports and Eurotunnel stations, and vice versa.

²⁴ More than a footnote: 351 deaths as at 9 August 2022, see <https://neocarto.github.io/calais/en/>

2020). Yeo (2020) suggests juxtaposed measures have allowed UK immigration officers to carry “out racial sifting, picking out and preventing the boarding of ethnic minorities, such as Roma from Eastern Europe, who were deemed more likely to claim asylum on arrival”.

Progressively stronger security measures considerably reduced migrants clandestinely boarding lorries and the Eurostar (Bertrand 2020) with the COVID-19 epidemic and exit of the UK from the EU marking the beginning of the surge of small boat crossings²⁵. By 2021 this had become the principal cross-Channel means for irregular migrants to reach the UK. As observed by the Women’s Refugee Commission (2019),

“Migration is like water, you cannot block it, you can only make the travel more difficult. If you block one route that was popular because it was less dangerous, so you force them to take a more dangerous route and people will arrive with more disease and more troubles.”

Figure 2: Map showing launch and arrival points of small boats in the Channel

Source: Milmo and Kirby (2021)

²⁵ See timelines for 1991-2020 (Boittiaux, 2020) and for 2020 (Timberlake, 2021)

‘Calais Jungle’ makes a mark

A humanitarian centre for migrants, predominantly from Kosovo at the time, was opened in Sangatte in northern France in September 1999 but closed in December 2002²⁶. Since then, migrants have established squats and makeshift camps which have in turn been destroyed by the authorities on a regular basis (Boittiaux, 2020).

After the closure of the Sangatte centre, a number of larger camps were established and destroyed around Calais²⁷, culminating in the creation of the ‘Calais Jungle’ at La Lande which in summer 2016 had up to 500 arrivals per week and a population of between 8–10,000 at its peak. Refugee Rights Europe (2016) found the Jungle had an “absence of formal refugee assistance by UNHCR and large NGOs that typically provide tailored services and protection in refugee settings around the world”. The French authorities demolished the camp in its entirety in October 2016. The timing dovetailed with the ‘2015 European Migrant Crisis’²⁸, when 1.3 million people came to the continent to request asylum (the most in a single year since World War II) and the height of UK public concerns about immigration. There was extensive and febrile attention and analysis locally and in Britain, France and further afield, with numerous perspectives at the time²⁹ and after³⁰.

Between April 2015 and October 2016, the French state opened the Jules Ferry Centre close to the Jungle, which welcomed 2,400 migrants daily and offered overnight accommodation for 400 women and children³¹. However, since its dissolution, “no similar provision has ever been created in Calais” (Refugee Resilience Collective in UKHoCHAC, 2022).

²⁶ The centre had a capacity of 200 people and the French Red Cross estimated 67,611 had transited during the time it was open.

https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Centre_d%27h%C3%A9bergement_et_d%27accueil_d%27urgence_humanitaire_de_Sangatte

²⁷ Migrants Info. Nord (2017) includes a video outlining the situation between 1999 and 2017.

²⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2015_European_migrant_crisis

²⁹ For example see overview in pp.461-478 of Agrier and Le Courant (2022), with other specific areas addressed ranging from: female case studies (Callaghan, 2015); children (UNICEF, 2016); structural ‘necropolitical’ violence (Davies, Isakjee and Dhesi, 2017); sexual and reproductive health provision (Finnerty, 2016); life for women (Massaad and Paccalin, 2015)

³⁰ After the Jungle, for example see: Care4Calais submission in UHoCHAC (2022); Gerlach, Timberlake and Welander (2021); Hagan (2019); Taylor (2021)

³¹ Accessed on 26 August 2022, curiously while the main page of the Centre (<http://julesferry.vieactive.fr/>) suggests it is closed, it also says potential volunteers should “remain on standby” and this webpage suggests it is still open (<http://julesferry.vieactive.fr/le-centre-jules-ferry/>).

Chapter 3. Normative and theoretical frameworks

This section builds on the definition of a ‘migrant’ (Box 1) for the purpose of this dissertation; outlines the principle international frameworks governing migration and refugees and for women’s rights; explains what ‘protection’ implies; summarizes push and pull factors that may drive migration decisions; and considers the concept of ‘wicked problems’.

The Global Compact for Safe, Orderly Migration (GCM) (United Nations 2018, July) provides a high-level framework for migration. It seeks to:

“ensure that the human rights of women, men, girls and boys are respected at all stages of migration, their specific needs are properly understood and addressed and they are empowered as agents of change. It mainstreams a gender perspective, promotes gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls, recognizing their independence, agency and leadership in order to move away from addressing migrant women primarily through a lens of victimhood.”

Three of the GCM 23 objectives are particularly relevant in the context of small boat Channel crossings:

- (3) Provide accurate and timely information at all stages of migration
- (7) Address and reduce vulnerabilities in migration
- (12) Strengthen certainty and predictability in migration procedures for appropriate screening, assessment and referral

‘Gender responsiveness’ is mentioned in all objectives. Accompanying the GCM, the Office of the UN High Commissioner of Human Rights (OHCHR) provides a series of resources on human rights aspects, including on irregular migration³².

Pécoud (2020) suggests the GCM has helped to increase the profile of migration on the international agenda, and can be considered as “a reaction to the ‘migration crisis’ and to states’ perceived inability to keep unauthorized migration under control”. However he adds that the GCM does not directly address a number of political dilemmas and has been argued to reluctantly address certain practices such as detention and be indifferent to certain issues

³² <https://www.ohchr.org/en/migration/global-compact-safe-orderly-and-regular-migration-gcm>

including gender. The respective roles of states and migrant agency are left out. Irregular migration is not directly addressed but runs through many of the objectives.

The sister Global Compact on Refugees (GCR) (United Nations, 2018 December) emphasizes the importance of disaggregated data³³ and the establishment of immediate reception arrangements for refugees, providing basic humanitarian assistance and essential services, with due respect to a variety of actors including gender. Addressing specific needs is noted as a particular challenge, and these include women at risk; trafficking in persons, sexual and gender-based violence; and sexual and gender-based violence, sexual exploitation and abuse on harmful practices. In terms of gender,

“States and relevant stakeholders will seek to adopt and implement policies and programmes to empower women and girls in refugee and host communities, and to promote full enjoyment of their human rights, as well as equality of access to services and opportunities – while also taking into account the particular needs and situation of men and boys.”

The GCR also notes:

Refugee movements often have a significant regional or subregional dimension. While the characteristics of regional and subregional mechanisms and groupings vary, they may, as appropriate, play an important role in comprehensive responses. Past comprehensive responses have also demonstrated the value of regional cooperation in addressing refugee situations in a manner which encompasses the political dimensions of causes.

Neither the GCM nor GCR are legally binding.

³³ “Disaggregation is the breakdown of observations, usually within a common branch of a hierarchy, to a more detailed level to that at which detailed observations are taken.” OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms (<https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=4337>)

International frameworks promoting women’s rights

Donnelly and Mutiah (2018) present States’ obligations under international law to protect women and girls in refugee camps. Timberlake (2020), a joint NGO letter to the French government, outlines the situation of women migrants in northern France and the international law under which the French state is bound to provide assistance. They emphasize the following:

The Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW)³⁴ includes attention to women trafficked across international borders, female refugees and asylum-seekers, and unaccompanied or undocumented female children outside their country of origin. It sets out the bases for application of ‘temporary special measures’ as a means of realizing de facto and/or substantive equality for women. It seeks to ensure women and girls’ civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights, lifelong dignity and protection from discrimination. This includes equal access, and special attention, to healthcare (Article 12), and education (Article 10). The CEDAW Committee General Recommendation (GR) No. 30 in conflict-affected areas is that refugee camps should provide sexual and reproductive health; respond to gender-based violence (GRs 19 and 35); and provide access to justice (GR 33)

Other related conventions include the 2011 Council of Europe *Istanbul Convention: Action against violence against women and domestic violence*; and the 1950 *European Convention on Human Rights*.

Protection

UNHCR’s description of protection³⁵, while applying to “the immediate aftermath of any refugee exodus”, also arguably serves as well in terms of guidance for meeting the human rights of the more vulnerable and impoverished irregular migrants during their journeys. Adapted below:

“Governments normally guarantee the basic human rights and physical security of their citizens. But when people become [irregular migrants] this safety net [may] disappear.”

³⁴ 18 December 1979: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-elimination-all-forms-discrimination-against-women>

³⁵ <https://www.unhcr.org/protection.html>

[Protection entails governments and organizations] “promot[ing] or provid[ing] legal and physical protection, and minimize the threat of violence – including sexual assault – which many [migrants] are subject to, even in countries of asylum[, with] at least a minimum of shelter, food, water and medical care.

The GCR states “Refugees and migrants are entitled to the same universal human rights and fundamental freedoms, which must be respected, protected and fulfilled at all times. However, migrants and refugees are distinct groups governed by separate legal frameworks”.

As is alluded to in Box 1, the ‘refugee or migrant’ argument bedevils much of the official discourse, which filters down to programming, particularly between UNHCR and IOM who (one could argue territorially) are speaking on behalf of each group separately. Reumert (2016) explores the question of this difference but summarizes:

“Refugees, defined by international humanitarian law as people in need of protection, are entitled to a privileged status. Once granted refugee status in a host country, the state can’t deport them. Migrants, on the other hand, live without legal protection and can be deported at any time.”

One way around this is to speak of ‘mixed migration’, ‘people on the move’ or ‘migrants and refugees’. In any case, it points to the sometimes uncomfortable reality that the different groups have different rights in international law, which unfortunately can get in the way of treating people decently, lead to individuals and institutions gaming the system, and act as a barrier to coordination. Reumert (2016) suggests all should be considered as asylum seekers, whether they are ‘true’ refugees or have been forced to migrate through insecurity, poverty, or hunger.

Push and pull factors

Figure 3 below summarizes the motivation factors, ‘push and pull’, that encourage migrants to move from their country of origin to country of destination. The motivations complement, and can particularly be compared with those elucidated in Box 5, as well as the ‘reasons behind women’s migration’ (Boyd and Grieco, 2003) reproduced in Annex 2.

Figure 3: Push and pull factors

Push-factors Countries of origin	➔	Migrants	←	Pull-factors Countries of destination
↓		Structure of differences in life chances		↓
Population growth, young age structure Inadequate educational institutions, medicare and social security	←	1. Demographic factors and social infrastructure	→	Stable population, population decline, demographic ageing Welfare state benefits, educational institutions, medicare, social security
Unemployment, low wages Poverty, low consumption and living standard	←	2. Economic factors	→	Labour demand, high wages Welfare, high consumption and living standard
Dictatorships, shadow democracy, bad governance, political upheaval Conflict, (civil)war, terrorism, human rights violation, oppression of minorities	←	3. Political factors	→	Democracy, rule of law, pluralism, political stability Peace, security, protection of human and civil rights, protection of minorities
Ecologic disaster, desertification, lack of natural resources, water shortage, soil erosion, lack of environmental policy	←	4. Ecological factors	→	Better environment, environmental policy, protection of natural resources and environmental protection
↓		Migrant networks		↓
Decisions of the family or the clan Information flows, media, transferred picture of country of origin Possibilities of (ir)regular immigration, routes of trafficking	←	5. Migrant flows and migrant stocks	→	Diaspora, ethnic community Information flows, media, transferred picture of destination country Possibilities of (ir)regular immigration (right of residence)

Source: Schmid (2018)

Grounded theory

Information collection and analysis for this dissertation was influenced by *grounded theory*, albeit without a fuller use of the iterative and filtering typically undertaken, given the process was principally desk-based. However it followed the principle that data was “systematically collected and analyzed ... to uncover such things as social relationships and behaviours of groups, known as social processes” (Noble and Mitchell, 2016). Features of grounded theory include:

- Data collection and analysis occur simultaneously;
- Categories [are] developed from data, [without] pre-existing conceptualization;
- Theoretical sampling is used to refine categories, constructed inductively;
- Social processes are discovered in the data.

Noble and Mitchell (2016) describe that theoretical sensitivity (the insight of the researcher) comes from:

1. literature—in-depth reading offers a rich understanding of the phenomena being studied;
2. professional and personal experience—offers an understanding of the events and topics being explored;
3. the analytic process—allows for insight and understanding of the phenomena.

The dissertation took shape by drawing on the broad range of material available, guided by my insights including as a British and a French citizen. The categorization presented in Chapter 6 and related analysis was also influenced by a systematic consideration of the material.

Wicked problems and politics

Interaction Design Foundation (2022) explains that “Wicked problems are problems with many interdependent factors making them seem impossible to solve”, with no definitive formula and factors that are often incomplete, in flux, and difficult to define. Characteristics³⁶ of wicked problems are (with underlined text referring to the issue of, and potential solutions to, the issue of Channel migrants):

- Every wicked problem is essentially unique
- Every wicked problem can be considered a symptom of another problem
- There is always more than one explanation for a wicked problem because the explanations vary greatly depending on the individual perspective
- Wicked problems do not have a set number of potential solutions
- Solutions to wicked problems are not true-or-false; they can only be [subjectively] good-or-bad
- There is no immediate test of a solution to a wicked problem, with no way to know if your solution is final

Like other wicked problems such as climate change (perhaps combining several areas as a mega wicked problem), the AIDS epidemic and social injustice, views about migration and how

³⁶ adapted from Rittel, H. W., & Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy sciences*, 4(2), 155-169, cited in Interaction Design Foundation (2022).

to solve it are multi-faceted. Proposed solutions are typically highly political, with “competition between [the] competing interest groups”³⁷, but to have a long-term solution which is practical and sustainable there is a need for compromise rather than leaning one ideological way or the other.

The notion of the wicked problem shaped the approach to this dissertation in that it has sought as broad as possible a range of views and perspectives on the issue.

Fictional perspectives

Murray (2017, pp.116–117) refers to Raspail’s 1973 novel *Le Camp des Saints* which portrays a dystopian mass migration of a million people from Calcutta into Europe on a fleet of boats, with others “watching and waiting to get on boats themselves”. Murray suggests that in response to being overwhelmed “not by force but by simply landing peaceably on their shores”, in an echo to contemporary responses by the UK and France:

“The politicians dither, incapable of working out what their attitude should be and flipping wildly between attempts to accept the armada and their ideas of how to scupper it”

Contrasting Raspail’s story about the movement of millions, Teulade (2016) presents a very different individual story (written for adolescents) of Jonas, a 15-year old Eritrean who reaches Calais after a long trip in search of a better life, encountering hardships and tragedy.

Both books present a bleak picture around migration, albeit with very different foci which are deliberately meant to “shake up people’s consciences”³⁸. Their markedly different underlying ideological positions well represent the gulf of perspectives coming from different ends of the political spectrum.

³⁷ Definition of ‘politics’, 3a, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/politics>

³⁸ See webpage promoting Teulade’s book at <https://www.lajoiedelire.ch/livre/petit-prince-de-calais/>

Chapter 4: Arriving in England and leaving (and living in) France

Arriving in England

In 2021, 28,526 people were detected arriving on small boats crossing the English Channel from France to Great Britain, out of 52,000 who attempted to cross³⁹. This compares with 8,466 in 2020, 1,843 in 2019 and 299 in 2018 (UK Home Office, 2022). The rise in this irregular and undocumented migration has generated considerable and polarized media attention, particularly following events with a significant loss of life, and in relation to UK Government proposals to address the issue.

There are a number of reasons why migrants seem to have, in general, more interest in coming to the UK rather than staying in France. At the beginning of the next section (on leaving, and living in, France) these pull and push factors are summarized in Box 5.

Box 2: People crossing the Channel in small boats since 2018: key statistics

- 87.4% of people crossing have been male, and 91% are aged 39 years or younger⁴⁰.
- In 2021, the principal nationalities of people were Iranian (30%), Iraqi (21%), Eritrean (22%) and Syrian (9%). Iranians represented the vast majority of small boat arrivals in 2018 (80%) and 2019 (66%), with a greater mix of nationalities detected making the crossing since 2020⁴¹. All of the five most represented nationalities are from countries disfigured by current or recent war⁴².
- 98% of people arrive without a passport⁴³.

⁴⁰ Migrant Watch UK (2022, March 9)

⁴¹ UK Home Office (2022, February 24)

⁴² However the proportions continue to change and, for example, “the numbers of Albanian migrants have increased exponentially and make up more than 60 per cent of those on some small boat crossings. Around 6,000 Albanians have reached Britain this way since the start of the year, including more than 700 in one day”. (Barrett, 2022)

⁴³ Migrant Watch UK (2022, March 1). Murray (2017, pp.71-72) comments “being unidentified is an advantage ... people can pretend to be other ages, other people, or either from another country” and (of Italy in the example but making the same argument of the UK) “it is hard to find cases of someone arriving being refused the right to remain and then being sent back to their home countries ... The truth is that once you survive [the Channel] then you are in [the UK] for good”. Yeo (2022) concurs, “The

The UK House of Commons Home Affairs Committee (UKHoCHAC 2022) on *Channel crossings, migration and asylum* published its report on 18 July, estimating 60,000 or more people were expected to arrive irregularly in small boats in 2022. The UK Home Office (2022, May 26) estimates that there were 55,146 asylum applications in total in the year to March 2022, suggesting that Channel migrants represented half of the total in 2021. Although the number of Channel migrants is due to increase in 2022, the proportion is likely to fall given the arrival of 100,000+ Ukrainian refugees.

Gathering inputs from a wide range of sources, the UKHoCHAC notes:

“There is no magical single solution to dealing with irregular migration. Detailed, evidence-driven, fully costed and fully tested policy initiatives are by far most likely to achieve sustainable incremental change that deters journeys such as dangerous Channel crossings. Close co-operation with international partners, particularly those in France, is equally essential, but has not always proved mutually forthcoming from across the Channel as this has become a very ‘political’ issue post-Brexit.”

The UK Home Office suggests 98% of people claim asylum once landed in the country (Migrant Watch UK, 2022). While Migrant Watch UK (2022) suggests “81% have been found by the authorities not to have a credible claim⁴⁴ ... in the UK” [and are not] “truly needy”, it is not clear where this data comes from and how it is backed up. Indeed the UK Home Office (2022, May 26) statistics report that among the top ten nationalities applying for asylum in the UK, the grant

reality is that even those who lose their asylum cases — an increasingly small minority — are likely to remain in the United Kingdom in the long term.”

⁴³ Migrant Watch UK (2022, March 1). Murray (2017, pp.71-72) comments “being unidentified is an advantage ... people can pretend to be other ages, other people, or either from another country” and (of Italy in the example but making the same argument of the UK) “it is hard to find cases of someone arriving being refused the right to remain and then being sent back to their home countries ... The truth is that once you survive [the Channel] then you are in [the UK] for good”. Yeo (2022) concurs, “The reality is that even those who lose their asylum cases — an increasingly small minority — are likely to remain in the United Kingdom in the long term.”

⁴⁴ The Migrant Watch UK submission to UKHoCHAC (2022) also highlights that UNHCR had pointed to ‘economic reasons’ as the most prominent factor motivating people who were gathering in Libya in 2016 to originally leave their country.

rate is above 80% (including 88% for Iranians and 98% for Syrians). Asylum Information Database (Aida, 2022) suggests overall there is a 72% acceptance rate in the UK⁴⁵.

Different perspectives around need and who to prioritize are at the heart of the political discussion about the issue of small boat irregular migration. UKHoCHAC (2022) observes that while safe asylum routes do exist for certain nationalities (e.g. Afghanistan and Ukraine⁴⁶) they do not exist for all countries. Many organizations providing submissions to the UKHoCHAC⁴⁷ argue that the only real solution is to create a safe and legal process/route to allow people to make a fair asylum claim without having to risk their lives crossing the Channel, including humanitarian pathways to admission such as indicated under section 67 of the 2016 UK Immigration Act⁴⁸. Other organizations⁴⁹ suggest going further, by more ambitiously tackling the root causes of displacement within UK government policy, more fundamentally addressing the threats to well-being, peace, security and prosperity in the countries from which migrants are coming.

Conversely, the submission from Migrant Watch UK in UKHoCHAC (2022) claims the majority of UK residents consider the Channel crossings to be a problem. For example, citing a survey by Redfield and Wilton Strategy (in August 2020), 63% of people felt that those crossing should not be allowed to settle in the UK, half said they should be sent back to France and 36% called for them to return to their home country. The poll also found that 73% agreed that the French should do more to stop people setting off on such trips. Migrant Watch UK notes that for the UK as a whole there had been a reduction in immigration staff and budgets, insufficient measures to prevent absconding, and a drop in enforced removals of failed asylum claimants (from 6,532 in 2009 to 1,742 in 2018).

⁴⁵ Percentages vary according to how the data is considered. For more on the UK asylum process, see The Migrant Observatory (2022, August 22).

⁴⁶ “more than 5,000 [Afghan refugees] in the first year and up to 20,000 over the coming years” (UK Government, 2022, August 5); and more than 100,000 Ukrainian refugees (UK Government, 2022 July 28)

⁴⁷ e.g. accompanying UKHoCHAC (2022), submissions from Amnesty International Care4Calais, IoM, The Refugee Council, Refugee Resilience Collective, UNHCR

⁴⁸ See also The Joint Council for the Welfare of Immigrants (2021) for its proposal on a humanitarian visa scheme

⁴⁹ e.g. accompanying UKHoCHAC (2022): separate submissions from Oxfam, Quakers in Britain et al

Box 3: Conditions of reception for small boat migrant arrivals in the UK

For this dissertation, it was possible to find a broader range of public documents in the UK than France which provide insights into conditions for migrants as they arrive. For example Neal (2022), in his capacity as Independent Chief Inspector of Borders and Immigration, catalogues in detail how the increasing volume of small boat migrant arrivals at times overwhelmed the immigration services. His report is extremely critical of the UK Home Office's response, for example suggesting data management is "inexcusably awful" and, in writing to the HM Chief Inspector of Prisons on 28 September 2021, stating that he had "never visited a detention facility in such a poor state." Publication of the report was delayed by the Home Office⁵⁰. A separate UK HM Chief Inspector of Prisons (2021) report on an unannounced inspection of the detention facilities of migrants at Dover and Folkestone was similarly critical.

Box 4: The costs of crossing the Channel and reaching Calais

Smugglers have been adept and reactive in effectively organizing small boats for Channel crossings, with Associated Press (2021) suggesting that they can earn up to 300,000 Euros for a single boat (the minimum total earnings for the year to 21 November 2021 being 69 million Euros). Sarwar (2021) posed as an economic migrant from Pakistan to learn more about their operation. Citing Mimi Vu, an expert of Vietnamese migration:

"Between coronavirus and Brexit, 'this is a golden age for the smugglers and organized crime because the countries are in disarray ... Think of it like a shipping and logistics company'." (Associated Press, 2021)

⁵⁰ See the Press Release from Mr Neal (Independent Chief Inspector of Borders and Immigration, UK Government, 2022) which criticized the Home Office for the 4-month delay.

Each migrant is charged an average of between 3,000–7,000 Euros for the trip, although there is evidence this is falling⁵¹. A couple of videos on Alex, a migrant from Iran, suggested that he had saved 9,000 Euros in total for the total voyage from Iran to the UK⁵². An interview with Milad and her uncle originated from Syria revealed that they had spent 5,000 Euros and spent 16 days on the road to reach the Calais Jungle (Massaad and Paccalin, 2015).

UNICEF (2016) found that women possessing the financial means and access to intermediaries reached France after an average of 45 days, but for the poorest and most vulnerable this could take many years⁵³. Bennhold (2016) cites Samar, a 35-year-old Syrian refugee: “Everybody knows there are two ways of paying the smugglers ... with money or with your body.”

It is suggested that in some instances, unaccompanied boys are deliberately sent by their family⁵⁴. Conversely it seems possible that a higher proportion of unaccompanied girls than boys may be migrating as a consequence of their own decision to escape constraints such as child marriage and limited educational and other future prospects⁵⁵.

Finally, Schmoll (2020) suggests some women crossing the Mediterranean may be trafficked for sex work and have debts imposed of between 30,000–80,000 Euros. She suggests there may be porosity between consent and coercion, with an underlying desire for self-affirmation and social mobility, leading some women to enter into a trafficked situation with a degree of willingness.

⁵¹ Additional estimates per passage cited in Institute of Race Relations (2020) - 3,000 UKP; Méheut. and Onishi (2021) - USD 1,100-2,800; UNICEF (2016) - between 5,000 - 7,000 Euros; and Wright and Fielding (2021) - 8,000 UKP for a family of six. Taylor (2022, September 4) cites one migrant who paid UKP 1,000, and said “The prices have dropped a lot ... It’s like the smugglers have a sale on at the moment.”

⁵² See Goudichaud, Ghobadi and Walsh (2021) as well as Goudichaud (2020) in which the situation of Alex is contrasted with migrants from South Sudan with more limited resources. Alex pays 2,800 Euros (two times), not making the trips due to fear and other circumstances, and is not able to claim back his money.

⁵³ One Ethiopian woman had left her country aged 14, taking 15 more years to arrive in France following forced labour in Libya, Greece and Italy. Another 17-year old Ethiopian woman had left her country aged 13 to escape from an arranged marriage, arriving quickly in Libya and working there as a maid for two years. During her long journeys she was frequently raped and had no other means of earning money.

⁵⁴ e.g. UNICEF (2016) “Families who do not have enough money to plan their departure together depend on the sending of one child (male) in order to ensure regular income and to open the way for other family members.”

⁵⁵ e.g. see Annex 3 or Ruth (BBC, 2016) and Winta (UNICEF, 2016)

There are also stories of migrants who have a much easier time crossing the Channel and arrive in the UK ready to cheat the system. Ryan (2022) profiles Elvis Zoto, a 19-year-old Albanian, who gloated of the ease of getting illegally into the UK:

“They keep you in detention a maximum of two days, then send you to a hotel. In the detention centre it’s good conditions. You tell them you are married and that’s the end of the story. You have to get away from the hotel and just wait for your relatives to get you in a car. I left from the window of that hotel . . . I disappeared . . . Keep a low profile and after a month get a solicitor.”

A popular UK perspective is that unregulated migrants should be simply turned back in the Channel or even, as proposed by the government in early 2022, sent to a third country such as Rwanda⁵⁶. Justification for this view is presented by Policy Exchange (2022), suggesting if the UK government fails to implement ‘Plan A’ (boat “interception, immediate turn-around and an escorted return”), a ‘Plan B’ involving deportation could be undertaken. Initial UK Government efforts to send migrants to Rwanda were held back, among other opposing parties, by the European Court of Human Rights in June 2022.

Conversely, the University of Bristol submission to UKHoCHAC (2022) cites Article 98 of the 1982 Law of the Sea Convention, to which the UK is a party. This requires States to render assistance to those in need/distress “with all possible assistance”. The UK is also bound to allow asylum claims at the border and cannot return most adult asylum seekers to France without considering their asylum claims⁵⁷. Boats can only be denied entry if it is known that they could safely return to another country, which is a judgment unlikely to be made for the fragile and over-full small boats bearing irregular migrants. The University of Bristol adds:

“the only effective method of limiting the flow of cross channel migration must lie in enhanced cooperation with the French authorities in either preventing departure or ensuring that those at sea within their own maritime zones are returned safely to shore”.

⁵⁶ The dissertation will not consider this but soon after UK Home Secretary’s announcement of the plan (Patel, 2022) a range of perspectives emerged, e.g. Beirnes and Davidoff-Gore (2022), Clyne (2022), Liddle (2022), Migration Watch UK (2022, May 5), or Nair (2022). See also Taylor (2022, September 4).

⁵⁷ “The UK government also stopped accepting new family reunification transfer applications after September 2020, ending the only practical legal option for UK entry available to unaccompanied children in other European countries.” (Human Rights Watch, 2021)

UKHoCHAC (2022) adds:

“Departure from the EU’s Dublin Regulation arrangements [due to Brexit] has resulted in far fewer returns to Europe and attempts to forge bilateral agreements with EU states have entirely failed, but the number of successful returns to EU countries had been dwindling and the policy had not been working well even before Brexit.”⁵⁸

Asylum seekers in the UK face an average waiting time for an initial decision of between one and three years (Refugee Council, 2021), with accommodation and support costs to the Home Office estimated to be at least UKP 8,765 per person (Hewett, 2021) and the overall annual cost of the asylum system being more than UKP 1.5 billion, which “the Government considers too high and unsustainable in the long term.” (UKHoCHAC, 2022)^{59, 60}.

The UK Government, already constrained by international law, is required to address the needs of the vast majority of migrants. Expelling them is only possible after processing their asylum claim (even then, there is scope for appeal and some people may abscond). Paradoxically, given the focus of Brexit around reducing irregular migration⁶¹, the government has been limited further in this regard as the country is no longer party to the EU Dublin Regulation arrangements. Meanwhile there has been an apparent neglect of government mechanisms to handle the increased number of irregular migrants and asylum seekers, despite signs that this would increase. There is also evidence that Ukrainian refugees and those from other

⁵⁸ The Dublin Regulation suggests people seeking international protection should be given priority in states where they have family members. With no links, “... the first Member State in which the application for international protection was lodged shall be responsible for examining it.” <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02013R0604-20130629>. The fear of being relocated to the first country in which a migrant arrived and sought asylum, often the case for many people in France who have passed through other European countries, can be a push factor to leave France (see Box 5).

⁵⁹ “At the end of March 2022, there were 89,344 cases (relating to 109,735 people) awaiting an initial decision, over double the number of applications awaiting an initial decision at the end of March 2020 (40,830, relating to 51,906 people)”. The number of asylum applications in the year ending March 2022 was “56% more than in the year ending March 2020 and the highest number for almost two decades” (UK Home Office, 2022 May 26).

⁶⁰ See The Migration Observatory (2020, September 10) for a good overview of irregular migration issues in the UK.

⁶¹ Also paradoxically in terms of regular immigration, Evans-Pritchard (2022) remarks that the June 2022 UK immigration statistics show that a record 1.1 million people were issued to live in the UK (with 331,000 work visas and the top 10 nationalities being non-European, headed significantly (111,000) by India. Worker visas require a minimum salary of UKP 25,600 or UKP 20,480 for some jobs on the shortage list. This suggests the “Rwanda camp for illegal migrants, if it ever happens, is an odd distraction within the greater picture.”

nationalities are treated differently, following a 'hierarchy of worthiness', for example "Ukrainians received immediate refugee status and lived in people's homes but Afghans were left in hotels for months" (BBC, 2022, August 1).

UKHoCHAC (2022) suggests:

"We have no reliable data on why migrants who have reached safe haven in European nation states are sufficiently desperate to reach the UK that they will risk their lives to cross the Channel in flimsy, unseaworthy dinghies and makeshift craft. The Home Office should seek to find out what draws people to the UK to help it develop sound future policy."

Based on available information, this statement seems naive. Incentives for migrants to reach the UK are very clear and are shown in Box 5.

Leaving, and living in, France

The French *Défenseur des droits* (2018) has expressed concerns since October 2015 that:

"for migrants in Calais, requesting asylum in France is not really a credible choice [compared to] going to Great Britain"⁶²

Migrants have pull factors to the UK but also strong push factors based on extremely unwelcoming conditions in the Calais region and France more broadly. The reports cited later in this section suggest this is due to a deliberate policy to ensure migrants' living conditions are regularly disturbed and highly unstable⁶³, a quagmire of French bureaucracy, and repeated incidents of rights violations and violence by the state itself. The situation has continued and even worsened since the destruction of the Calais Jungle in 2016, with Keen (2019) suggesting that this "theatre of deterrence" is no accident with measures being a "kind of humanitarian abandonment".

⁶² "Dès octobre 2015, le Défenseur des droits a exprimé ses inquiétudes sur le fait que demander l'asile en France était pour les exilés de Calais une alternative peu crédible au choix de partir en Grande-Bretagne." (p.54, Défenseur des droits, 2018)

⁶³ Davies, Isakjee and Dhesi (2017) suggest this is an example of 'necropolitics': "when life [is] not so much being governed, as much as death itself [is] being sanctioned"

Box 5: Why do migrants cross the Channel to go the UK? – pull (and some push) factors

- They speak English better than French⁶⁴
- Many already have contacts (family⁶⁵ or friends) and networks in the UK
- The UK has a significantly higher Human Development Index (HDI) score than the origin countries of migrants⁶⁶
- The perception that it is easier to find work in the UK⁶⁷, including illegally⁶⁸, which is well remunerated⁶⁹, suggesting that economic reasons are important for many
- It is not obligatory in the UK to carry a national identity document
- The percentage of overall asylum rejections at first instance was 72.3% in France and 28% in the UK (Asylum Information Database (Aida), 2022) and the process for claiming asylum is radically different. There may also be incentives to apply for asylum in the UK if asylum claims have been refused in other countries or there are difficulties or fears due to the Dublin system⁷⁰
- Over time, the number of failed asylum claimants removed from the UK has fallen⁷¹.
- Perceptions of the moral right to come to the UK given history (and its injustices)⁷².
- Reports consistently report migrant perceptions that life in the UK is better, safer and more humane than in France (Refugee Rights Europe, 2016). “the hostile environment [in the Calais is] created by the policies at the border pushes people who find themselves stranded there to take undue risks with their lives by crossing the Channel to escape the systemic violence that is being perpetrated” (Human Rights Observers, 2022). “Living in liminal and precarious conditions in Northern France can act as a strong impetus to try and get to the UK by any means possible” (Welander, 2019). There are indications that racism is high in France compared to other countries⁷³.
- Conversely, crossing the Channel carries a “high chance of success at comparatively low risk” and “possibly as many as 70% are successful”, with lower risk of dying than crossing the Mediterranean in a small boat or on a train or a lorry. There are also reliably working coast guards in the Channel (Müller, 2021).

⁶⁴ A survey of 870 individuals in the Calais Jungle (Refugee Rights Europe, 2016) found that 56% had good spoken English compared to 4.8% with good spoken French.

- “The topography of the French Channel coast ... favours casting off in an areas of about 150 kilometers between Boulogne-sur-Mer and Dunkirk, [which] can only be monitored with a high level of personnel and technical efforts⁷⁴” (Müller, 2021)

IOM (2021) includes an analysis of 1,100 female responses (of those entering Europe between 2018–2020) that outline their reasons for migration:

- [Push] - 51% reported fear of violence or actual personal violence suffered as a primary reason for leaving [their country of departure], a share that is 17 percentage points higher than those among male respondents (33%) in the whole sample”.
- [Pull] - 30% of the whole sample reported that the choice was guided by the appealing socio-economic conditions of the destination country, while others mentioned the fact

⁶⁵ Many more female than male asylum seekers obtain family reunion asylum grants in the UK (see Chapter 6 and The Migrant Observatory (2022, August 22).

⁶⁶ HDI: Armenia (0.776), Eritrea (0.459) Iran (0.783), Iraq (0.674), South Sudan (0.433), Syria (0.567), United Kingdom (0.932), from <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/hdi-by-country>

⁶⁷ For example, “compared with countries such as Greece or France” (British Future in UKHoCHAC (2022)).

⁶⁸ The OECD (2018) shows estimates of irregular migrant populations, representative of potential illegal employment, at 0.4-8% in the EU-27 and 0.73% in the UK; the Migrant Data Portal (2022) suggests the EU-27 percentage is 0.3%-0.7% in the EU-27 and 1% in the UK. This implies that the proportion of irregular migrants in the UK is approximately twice that of the EU-27. Hymas (2022, August 23) cites an Albanian immigration source “The Albanians are coming for economic reasons. There is huge poverty in Albania and they want to get to the UK for a better life and good employment. Most end up working in the black market, especially in construction.” UNICEF (2016) suggest that upon arrival in the UK, Afghan and Iranian children have to work to repay money loaned by their family and community to pay for their journey, with British authorities indicating places of “exploitation were the catering sector (kebab houses and other fast food restaurants), car washes, hairdressing salons and barber shops”.

⁶⁹ Compare the situation of undocumented Brazilians in Geneva, with an upper middle income country and Switzerland, a high income country, where a domestic worker earning CHF 25 per hour can earn as much in one day as the minimum monthly salary in Brazil (Sunderland, 2022).

⁷⁰ Research for this dissertation did not, aside from occasional details gleaned from individual stories, identify any concrete information on which countries migrants had passed through and/or applied for asylum. The reticence of migrants to share such information is understandable given fears of being deported back to a country earlier in their journey.

⁷¹ “Enforced removals of failed asylum claimants fell from 6,432 in 2009 to 1,742 in 2018” (Migrant Watch UK submission to UKHoCHAC (2022)).

⁷² For example the Quaker submission in UKHoCFAC (2022) cites an asylum seeker “Why can I not ask if the UK want me? Many people in my village have the names of the British who were there to take the land before, your grandfathers, James, William. Many have these names.” See also the video from Raudot de Chatenay et al (2021) with (at 10:50) altercations between migrants and police officers who have prevented a small boat launching, “you make [problems in Africa], you steal my oil”.

⁷³ The Quaker submission to the UKHoCHAC (2022) notes “In a European Social Survey in the last decade, respondents in 26 countries were asked whether victims of all races were treated equally. Belgium was ranked 21st (40.9% answering yes) and France was ranked 24th (31.6% answering yes).”

⁷⁴ Keen (2020) cites Sénat who quotes French police as suggesting “they were being asked to empty the sea with a teaspoon.”

that it was the only choice available given the circumstances (21%), that the choice was made due to safety reasons (16%), or because they had some relatives (14%) or a network of conationals (6%) at the indented destination.

Yeo (2020) suggests that ‘destination preferences’ are rarely shaped by the deterrent or other migration policies of receiving countries⁷⁵. Rather, a wide range of factors shape immigration decisions, including “access to protection and family reunification, the availability/accuracy of information, the overall economic environment and social networks”⁷⁶.

This dissertation highlights three main reports, found to provide the most comprehensive and recent insight into conditions faced by migrants, which also criticize the current situation in the Calais. The first is the in-depth Assemblée Nationale de France report considering migration in France (Krimi and Nadot, 2021, which is similar to but a year before the UKHoCHAC 2022 enquiry, although with a broader overall focus. The others are Défenseur des droits⁷⁷ (2018 with 2020 update) and Human Rights Watch (2021). Conversely, Bertrand (2020), while also critical of the situation, presents the achievements from the perspective of the French state (e.g. following the destruction of the Calais Jungle, the number of migrants reduced from around 8,000 in 2016 to around 300 in 2019, with commensurately large reductions in direct intrusions in the sites of Eurotunnel and Port de Calais, reductions in the number of migrants in trucks, and the arrest of more than 1,700 smugglers between 2018 and 2019).

However, a recurring criticism is that closing one means of crossing the Channel leads to migrants finding other alternative means, as demonstrated by the increase in small boat crossings. Human Rights Watch (2021) suggests “some 2,000 migrants, including hundreds of unaccompanied children, are living in and around disused warehouses and under bridges in and around Calais. Several hundred more are staying in a forest in Grande-Synthe”.

UNICEF (2016) found that migrants were in regular movement between other cross-Channel ports, the north of Europe, or Paris as a “rear base”. The lack of links between child protection

⁷⁵ Citing Crawley, H. and Hagen-Zanker, J., ‘Deciding Where to go, Policies, People and Perceptions Shaping Destination preferences’

⁷⁶ Yeo adds that a UK Home Office Research Study (243) published in July 2002 considered this, by Robinson, V. and Segrott, J., ‘Understanding the decision-making of asylum seekers’

⁷⁷ French Public Defender of Rights, see <https://www.defenseurdesdroits.fr/>

services in these departmental councils made “the monitoring and support of unaccompanied children very problematic”.

Since October 2016, the French state has applied a ‘zero fixed point’⁷⁸ policy which aims to move on migrants as soon as they settle in one place in the region⁷⁹. Human Rights Observers (2021) call this a ‘scorched earth’ policy, creating constant insecurity and instability for migrants, and reported a total of 1,287 evictions in Calais and Grande-Synthe in 2021, with migrants fearing forcible evictions an average of 4.5 times a week without a court order and typically occurring with little advance warning, and often using tear gas⁸⁰. The Défenseur des droits reported in 2015 that Calais had become the city with the highest ratio of police officers per inhabitant in France⁸¹ (Keen, 2020) and Hagan (2019) reports that in 2018 there were 1,130 police and gendarmes stationed in the region – almost double the number of migrants (600) that the authorities estimated to be present. Tazzioli (2019) suggests that the state operates continued dispersal as a means of control. Cockerell (2021) remarks, “In Calais, everyone is watching each other”

Human Rights Watch (2021) reports that local authorities have placed legal and practical restrictions on humanitarian assistance, with aggressive policing extending to local groups providing aid. In addition to the regular destruction or seizure of tents and other personal items during evictions, the installation of fences and barriers in some areas forces migrants to walk further for food and water.

From the perspective of Calais residents, a review of articles about migrants in the newspaper *La Voix du Nord* between 2019 and 2022⁸² revealed that 65% of residents felt that migrants

⁷⁸ “Le ministre de l’Intérieur déclarait ainsi, dans une interview accordée à La Voix du Nord le 24 octobre 2016, que le gouvernement avait « une stratégie globale pour éviter qu’un point de fixation ne se reforme ».” Défenseur des droits (2018)

⁷⁹ Hagan (2019) suggests “The Jungle tainted France’s hospitable self-image, and the state is determined to prevent its re-emergence at all costs” and “It is obvious that routine shelter destruction is designed to punish migrant presence at the border, and yet the violent policy is shrouded in a discourse of environmental protection.”

⁸⁰ In 2018, 91.8% of migrants surveyed reported having experienced police violence whilst in France (Refugee Resilience Collective, submission to UKHoCFAC (2022). 77.8% of migrants in the Calais Jungle reported having been on the receiving end of tear gas, with one woman suggesting she had experience a miscarriage because of this (Refugee Rights Europe, 2016).

⁸¹ As well as being considered as a kind of punishment posting (Keen, 2020).

⁸² Held in the Médiathèque Louis Aragon, <http://www.mediatheque.calais.fr/>

were vectors of insecurity, with 22% finding that their presence posed difficulties⁸³. While some residents in the region support associations providing food and other support to migrants⁸⁴, others oppose such interventions and were fed up with the situation, criticizing migrants for various reasons including being violent, leaving waste, menacing children at bus stops, and their presence causing house prices to fall in some cases by over 100,000 Euros. In the June 2022 legislative elections, approximately 29% of the vote in the three *circonscriptions* between Calais and Dunkirk⁸⁵ was for the far right *Rassemblement Nationale (RN)*⁸⁶.

Extreme cases of hostility seemed relatively common: in the Calais Jungle, Keen (2020) reported cases with migrants menaced by “groups of up to 20 operating on the periphery of the camp, with aggression ranging from yelling, spitting, insulting, holding noses, kicking, beating with sticks and hitting with glass bottles from moving vehicles”⁸⁷. For all concerned, in its precarity and chaos the Calais Jungle became known as the “worst refugee camp in the world” (Gerlach, Timberlake and Welander, 2021) but after it was bulldozed, conditions for migrants became even worse⁸⁸.

Compared to France, the process for *beginning* an asylum claim in the UK, while not without its problems, is transparent, fast, and relatively straightforward⁸⁹. In contrast, the Défenseur de droits (2018) suggests the French system is saturated, difficult to access, and that finding information about it is a significant challenge. Taylor’s (2022, August) article suggests little has changed in the subsequent four years. The Défenseur de droits (2018) identified a survey of 2,950 asylum seekers in Paris which found that 66.9% were unable to access information on

⁸³ Based on two surveys, of 608 individuals, in November 2019 and March 2021, reported in *La Voix du Nord* on 7 May 2021.

⁸⁴ Three French citizens even conducted a hunger strike against the inhuman conditions facing migrants (Le Monde avec AFP, 2021).

⁸⁵ Nord 13, Nord 14, and Pas-de-Calais 7. Conversely, the mayors of Dunkirk and Grande-Synthe are left-wing and have a more tolerant discourse towards migrants – e.g. compare Mayor of Grande-Synthe (2020), notably differently politically to Bertand (2020) for the Hauts-de-France Regional Council, or Franceinfo (2020) including the Mayor of Grande-Synthe’s “Policy in favour of migrants”.

⁸⁶ The RN gained a record 17.3% of the popular vote in the second round of the French legislative elections, winning 89 out of 577 seats nationally ([https://www.interieur.gouv.fr/Elections/Les-resultats/Legislatives/elecresult_legislatives-2022/\(path\)/legislatives-2022/FE.html](https://www.interieur.gouv.fr/Elections/Les-resultats/Legislatives/elecresult_legislatives-2022/(path)/legislatives-2022/FE.html))

⁸⁷ “45.8% of women in the Calais Jungle reported experiencing violence by non-police citizens, e.g. verbal and racist abuse, throwing bottles” (Refugee Rights Europe, 2016)

⁸⁸ A Kurdish Iraqi “man was asked if he ever considered claiming asylum in France, he replied, ‘Of course I did. But it’s unviable. The French police showed me that they hate refugees there. There is no future for refugees there. If they treat homeless refugees with that much hatred, I don’t want to be part of their society’ (Refugee Resilience Collective, submission to UKHoCFAC, 2022).

⁸⁹ See Neal (2022) and UK HM Chief Inspector of Prisons (2021)

how to make a claim. The Manager of the Jules Ferry Centre (Kleihauem, 2015) “indicated only 60 out of 600 women asked for migration in France; most had their family or husband in the UK”. Krimi and Nadot (2021) found that it was not possible to visit the majority of *préfectures* in France in person (only via online application) and also criticize significant difficulties faced by migrants to obtain medical care (AME)⁹⁰. Providing a case study of Oula Alhindy, a Syrian woman aged 47 years, who came to France in 2014 and eventually but after a considerable struggle obtained French nationality, Nadot suggests “the incompetent French authorities are not equal to their humanitarian responsibilities”⁹¹.

However Richards and Timberlake (2019) suggest there are considerable differences between accommodation centres for women in France:

“Some facilitate access to local hospitals and dentists, provide hygiene products and clothing, and create supportive relationships with those living in the centre. In these conditions, more families choose to claim asylum in France.”

In terms of budgets, Krimi and Nadot (2021) report that in 2020 expenses in the Calais linked to migrant populations were EUR 160 million, of which EUR 40 million were received from UK authorities, The net cost to France of EUR 120 million can be compared to being one and a half times that of OFRPA (the French organization protecting refugees and apatrides) that processes nearly 100,000 asylum requests in the year. Krimi and Nadot note that 85% of the expenses were for security purposes with the remaining 15% dedicated to health, social and humanitarian support, suggesting security firms have been a stakeholder benefitting from the allocations.

Recommendation of 22 of Krimi and Nadot (2021) is to end the ‘zero fixed point’ policy and establish local units in the coastal area to provide support to the migrants. Recommendations 13 and 15 are to provide an alternative and more accessible system for migrants to access *préfectures*, and to reduce obstacles to access AME. Recommendation 23 is to “Make issues faced by migrant women an integral dimension of migration and integration policies”⁹².

⁹⁰ AME, L'aide médicale de l'État

⁹¹ See pp.40-44. “Les administrations françaises, incompétentes, ne se montrent pas à la hauteur de leur tâche humanitaire”.

⁹² “Faire des problématiques que rencontrent les femmes migrantes une dimension à part entière des politiques de migration et d'intégration”

Differences between the British and French

France and the UK have had a love-hate relationship for centuries, with the situation in the Channel deepening antagonism despite the various treaties designed to structure the Channel border relationship. After the tragic deaths of 27 people when a boat capsized in the Channel on 27 November 2021, Landler (2021) observed:

“Rather than working together to curb hazardous sea crossings, leaders of the two countries almost immediately fell into a familiar pattern of squabbling” [which was not] “helped by the acrimonious back-and-forth between French and British officials that led France on Friday to rescind an invitation for Britain’s Home secretary, Priti Patel, to attend an emergency meeting on the crisis.

...

Prime Minister Boris Johnson and President Emmanuel Macron almost immediately fell into a familiar pattern: questioning each other’s motives, seeking to score political points and casting blame for an intractable global problem that afflicts both their countries.

...

The best the two can hope for is a sharply reduced flow [of irregular migration], and even that would require a degree of cooperation that seems wishful thinking in the current strained atmosphere.”

From a French perspective in terms of managing migration flows, Bertrand (2020) of the Hauts-de-France Regional Counsel, wrote:

“If no progress is made [by the British to help French police efforts], the Hauts-de-France Regional Council will ask that the French Government denounce the Treaty of Le Touquet, in order to completely revisit the organization of the Franco–British border. The 1st January 2021 Brexit date makes this option increasingly likely. France can no longer accept having to organize the British border if the United Kingdom is unwilling to take its part in securing and stabilizing this border.”

Indeed Krimi and Nadot (2021) suggest that the budget division for policing/supporting migrants in Calais (mentioned in the section above) is “hardly favourable to France”⁹³. Conversely, in November 2021 UK Prime Minister Boris Johnson suggested efforts by the French to stop small boat crossings hadn’t “been enough”⁹⁴.

At a very different level, De Cloet (2018) volunteered with associations in northern France and described the experience. She compares the French approach as top-down, distant, “functional and fast while adhering to a more hierarchical organizational structure”, and “all about equal distribution and the same for everyone”. This compares to that of the “idealistic” ... British grassroots [organizations which were seen to be] way too closely involved, reckless, and too indulgent with refugees” and (from their perspective at least) had a “more humane” approach.⁹⁵ Overall, De Cloet commented:

“French and English organizations tend to disagree over a lot of things, and cultural differences is often pointed to as the reason for struggles in communication”

Overall, the cultural and linguistic differences between the UK and France play a significant factor in terms of how the situation is managed differently at all levels, from political to operational, and viewed by the public.

⁹³ “De ce point de vue, les accords de coopération conclus à ce jour avec le Royaume-Uni sont peu favorables à la France.”

⁹⁴ The Local (2022, April 15)

⁹⁵ De Cloet (2018) said two UNHCR staff in Calais (who incidentally had been criticized by volunteers for receiving a full-time salary and passing judgment on associations) had, speaking in a personal capacity, observed British “volunteers totally effacing themselves and becoming completely burnt out.” Separately, De Cloet’s candid personal testimony, ‘We are not professionals’, is a striking example of how offering well-meaning help may end up aggravating a situation. She and two other volunteers paid for a woman migrant and her two children to stay in a hotel in Calais, and rang social services to report this; subsequently the police arrived and took the children into care, leaving the mother alone and anxious about how to reunite with them.

Chapter 5: Using a gender lens to examine perspectives of migration

The remainder of this report focuses more explicitly on the experience of women and girls, while recognizing that gender is just one of a number of elements influencing migration. Gender definitions and relations should neither be considered as preponderant nor as binary, and also change as we evolve as individuals and societies. UNHCR (2022) notes:

“Gender denotes the socially constructed roles of women and men, which are often central to the way in which people define themselves and are defined by others. Unlike sex, gender is not a biological determinant. Gender roles are learned, may change over time, and vary within and between cultures. Gender often defines the duties, responsibilities, constraints, opportunities and privileges of women, men, girls and boys in any context.”

IOM recognizes that “a person’s sex, gender, gender identity and sexual orientation shape every stage of the migration experience” – including “functions, expectations, relations and dynamics” (Granda 2021) – and that “gender is central to any discussion of the causes and consequences of migration”. This is important to bear in mind, as UNHCR (2022) outlines:

“If processes and programs are gender exploitative, gender blind, or neutral, they may perpetuate (or even increase) gendered harm, while reducing the extent to which services can engage and support refugees, particularly women and girls. Gender sensitive and transformative programs, by contrast, integrate a gender lens and address and include gender to increase impact and equality.”

Annex 2 elaborates the five-level framework of gender responsiveness. Including gender-biased, -blind, -sensitive, -specific and -responsive. Annex 2 also outlines the GAM (Gender with Age Marker) framework elaborated by the humanitarian coordination forum, the Inter-Agency Standing Committee⁹⁶, which is used to assess projects for 12 essential programme

⁹⁶ <https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/the-inter-agency-standing-committee>

elements known as Gender Equality Measures or GEMs. The four main components of the GAM consider:

- Gender analysis: The needs, roles and dynamics of women, girls, boys and men in different age groups are understood
- Tailored activities: Women, girls, boys and men in different age groups get the right resources
- Influence on project: Women, girls, boys and men in appropriate age groups influence decisions throughout the project
- Benefits: Women, girls, boys and men in different age groups get different benefits

The final part of Annex 2 presents dimensions, indicators and key questions to consider when analyzing migration narratives from a gender perspective, and the reasons behind women's migration, including individual, family and societal factors.

Boyd and Grieco (2003) note that the interests of men and women do not always coincide and "may affect decisions about who manages to migrate, for how long, and to what countries", with a reminder of their observation that:

There are three distinct stages where gender relations, roles, and hierarchies influence the migration process and produce differential outcomes for women: the pre-migration stage, the transition across state boundaries, and the experiences of migrants in the receiving country.

And furthermore:

"by implicitly defining immigrant women as "dependent" and men as "independent", immigration policies of receiving societies place women in a "family role" rather than a "market role". This, in turn, can reinforce some of the factors responsible for the social vulnerability of migrant women.

This may be manifested in the way that women and girls are pigeon-holed and channelled to 'female' occupations, at any stage of migration but particularly in the receiving country, such as

domestic work, childcare, garment manufacturing, and/or even sex work as well as relate to the burden of 'female' roles, such as caring for children and other dependents, and housework⁹⁷.

Connell (1995) suggests that 'masculinity' exists in contrast with 'femininity'. Plummer (2004) unpacks four roles of hegemonic masculinity – compared to subordinate masculinity – which include avoiding the feminine; desire to be a 'big fish', embodying success, authority and exemplariness; bravery, confidence, reliability; and violence and boldness. Such identities may mean men are prone to aggression, unwilling to seek medical assistance and take more risks, and be burdened with a provider role. Migration may mean natural role models (e.g. fathers and uncles) are absent. Gender binaries in migration imply that men should engage in conflict while women and children escape from it (Allsopp, 2017), and exacerbate specific gender-related vulnerabilities. For example, the majority of detected victims of trafficking for sexual exploitation have been female, while more than half of identified victims trafficked for forced labour were men (UNODC, 2018). When migrants are detained, women face different exposure to physical and verbal abuse, as well as differentially experiencing mental ill health (PICUM, 2018).

⁹⁷ See European Institute for Gender Equality (2017) for gender-related issues for migrants settling into their country of arrival

Box 6: LGBTQI+ people

PICUM (2018) notes that in detention, LGBTQI+ migrants can be particularly exposed to social isolation and subject to physical and sexual violence, especially (and usually) when they are held with men. Same sex intercourse is criminalized in many countries (and in some subject to the death penalty) which may exacerbate lack of reporting around any abuses during migration, leading to difficulty in obtaining data and testimonies around LGBTQI+ (UNODC, 2021). LGBTQI+-related stigma and discrimination may lead to harassment, exclusion, sexual violence, or other forms of violence in any country. While EU asylum law recognises sexual orientation and gender identity as exclusive reasons for persecution, not all Member States recognise gender expression and sex characteristics as a ground for protection, either in laws or in practice (ILGA-Europe, 2021).

Research for this dissertation did not focus on the situation of LGBTQI+ migrants nor, it should be added, encounter much information about this group related to irregular migration across the Channel. A report (UK Government, 2021) indicated that 3% of all asylum claims in 2020 were on the basis of sexual orientation, with Pakistan accounting for 14% of the applications, and 50% of claims from Uganda having an LGB element⁹⁸. However data indicates only a small proportion of these nationalities crossed the Channel. A separate study in Italy conducted in 2014–2015 found that 4% of asylum seekers reported fleeing their home country due to persecution on the basis of sexual orientation (Women’s Refugee Commission, 2019). It is speculated that a higher-than-average proportion of migrants using the Channel route may be LGBTQI+, with this identity probably deliberately concealed due to fear of discrimination and ill-treatment.

Representations of gender binaries are particularly visible in stereotypes around migration and gender, explored in the next section.

An absence of protection systems means perpetrators can abuse with impunity. UNFPA (2018) notes that “lack of shelter, overcrowding in camps and poorly lit public toilets all increase the risk

⁹⁸ Noting also SOGICA, Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity Claims of Asylum Project (2020) which compares key issues of SOGI asylum rights in Germany, Italy and the UK.

of gender-based violence, including sexual violence”. Furthermore, “families under extreme hardship may also adopt coping mechanisms that jeopardize women’s and girls’ welfare. A separate UNFPA-supported study also “found alarming rates of child marriage among some vulnerable Syrian refugee populations”.

In summary, given the variety of structural, cultural and social factors, women are more vulnerable than men during migration. “Migrant women are statistically at greater risk of dying along the migration routes and while crossing the Mediterranean than male migrants” and “they are also more exposed to systematic violence, which often assumes a sexualized or gendered form” (Plambech, Henriksen and Chemlali, 2021). Women face double discrimination (as women as well as migrants) and face a more complex range of sexual and reproductive health issues than men, not least that they may become or be pregnant when on the move. As a consequence, women and girls are more likely to face health problems (UNFPA, 2018).

The lived experiences of women migrants seeking to cross the Channel are considered in detail in Chapter 6 and Annex 3. A diagrammatic summary is found in Figure 4 relating to women who were in the Calais Jungle. Schmoll (2020) considers some of the issues facing women migrants who cross the Mediterranean which include:

- exposure to different forms of violence;
- the challenges, ambivalences and delays associated with processes of welcome and asylum seeking;
- how societies where a migrant arrives may at the same time be warm, distant and/or paternalistic;
- tensions in autonomy and power (throughout the voyage and during related processes);
- constant reorientations of trajectory (opportunities, obstacles, good and bad encounters);
- multiple renouncements (ranging from, for example, separating from family at the country of departure, to perceptions of Europe and countries of arrival).

Figure 4: Issues that faced women in the Calais jungle

Source: La Plateforme des Soutiens aux Migrant.e.s (2019)

Stereotypes

Stereotypical depictions of migrants are pervasive within media, policy-making, and humanitarian debates, discourses, and interventions. Table 1 summarizes the main representations, and how they differ by gender. These are typically underlaid by rigid [binary] gender essentialism, where men and women are associated with “mutually exclusive and oppositional attributes” (Carpenter 2005). Women are more often seen as helpless victims⁹⁹, while men are much more portrayed as threats/criminals.

⁹⁹ Recalling the GCM call for a “move away from addressing migrant women principally through a lens of victimhood”.

This language oversimplifies complex individual stories and often appears in (political) discourse, the media and populist dialogue, underpinning the contrast of the portrayal of anarchic/hopeless (inferior) 'others' compared to an orderly/altruistic (superior) 'self'. In Rudyard Kipling's (1899) imperialist *White Man's burden*, foreign populations are viewed as 'half devil and half child', discourse which Połońska-Kimunguyi (2022) suggests is quietly present in contemporary media discourses of migration. Indeed, enduring connections exist between current inequalities and colonial pasts, with one racist and sexist trope suggesting that 'white men are saving brown women from brown men'¹⁰⁰.

National borders may also encourage the utilization of nationalized and military labels. Using 'migrant' as a catch-all, especially when this suggests people are 'illegal' economic immigrants, can delegitimize refugees' claims and right to asylum.

Gray and Franck (2019) show how narratives around migrants can change rapidly, using the mass influx of undocumented refugees to Europe showing a pivot for many from viewing migrants as victims to threats (or from compassion to moral panic). A first phase, 'Refugees welcome' was established from September to early November 2015. The terrorist attacks in Paris on 13 November 2015 (up until the end of the year) abruptly changed many people's views in a second phase, 'Paris changes everything'. Then a third phase began at the end of 2015, with the New Year's Eve violence in Cologne and elsewhere, as 'Sexual Jihad'.

¹⁰⁰ Gayati Spivak noted in Gray and Franck (2019)

Table 1: Gendered stereotypes of migrants

Key: Typically associated with women (normal text); *men (italic)*; all people (underlined)

Stereotype	Associated images (<i>men in italics</i>)
<p>Victim/vulnerable 'child'¹⁰¹</p>	<p>'Womenandchildren', including pregnant women. 'Pure'</p> <p>Suffering from gendered (sexual) violence (e.g. including sex slavery, rape, human trafficking)</p> <p>Need 'saving' from oppressive cultures and the hardships of their journeys</p> <p>Possible implication that can be 'protected' by staying at home</p> <p><u>Injured, elderly and disabled</u></p> <p><u>Voiceless, passive, powerless</u></p> <p><u>Devoid of agency</u></p> <p><i>Loving 'family men' (father/provider) who bear and manage their own and their families' physical and emotional vulnerability</i></p> <p><i>Adolescent men may be seen as desexualized</i></p>
<p>Heroines and <i>heroes</i></p>	<p>Brave and empowered, supporting their families and protecting children</p> <p>Emancipated (possibly 'Westernized') with good values</p> <p>Suggest that with the technology/other means, women 'help themselves'</p>

¹⁰¹ In Sicily, women migrants (but not men) who have died in the Mediterranean are given a dignified funeral. "When women and children die [at sea], they are no longer associated with the image of the 'irregular migrant', but become an example of the eternal sacrifice. Women specifically become examples of the purity of the dead, they transcend their historical circumstances, to become icons of the image of the woman: pure, virgin, mother"; UNODC (2021) citing an expert in the field of dead and missing migrants in Sicily.

	<i>Loving ‘family men’</i>
Threat/menace ‘devil’	<p><u>‘Enemies at the gate’ who pose a threat to the physical safety, security, the economy and identity – for example by seeking to access welfare and resources (in place of more worthy candidates)</u></p> <p><u>Language suggesting catastrophe and disaster: e.g. wave, flow, surge, swarm¹⁰²; needing to ‘close the tap’ of migration</u></p> <p><i>Ignorant young single men with ‘hegemonic’ violent, aggressive and dominant behaviour: hypersexualized, potential rapists and terrorists – “a cultural time-bomb, brought up in a different era ... incompatible with modern life” (Hopkins, 2016)</i></p>
‘Maid’ or ‘Prostitute’	Typically applied to women migrants in their receiving country, usually implying subordination and dependence

Adapted from Allsopp (2017), Gray and Franck (2019), Plambech, Henriksen and Chemlali (2021) and Połowska-Kimunguyi (2022); also compare particularly with the ‘dimensions, indicators and key questions to consider when analyzing migration narratives from a gender perspective’ in Güell and Parella (2021, reproduced in Annex 2).

Following these stereotypes and perspectives, Leprince (2022) presents evidence (since the 18th century up to the 2022 Ukrainian war) that, compared to male refugees, female refugees have been privileged and viewed more favourably and with more tolerance by receiving countries.

¹⁰² In 2015 the then UK Prime Minister David Cameron said “you have got a swarm of people coming across the Mediterranean seeking a better life, wanting to come to Britain” - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bx_f_oE6oFk

Figure 5: Selected cartoon depictions of Channel migrants

Stereotypes tend to be more easily seen in cartoons than in (typically more nuanced) narrative.

¹⁰³ "... illegal opportunists — mostly young men, some claiming to be children — barge their way in ahead of genuine asylum seekers from war-torn countries such as Ukraine and Afghanistan"

Chapter 6: The experiences and perspectives of women and girl Channel migrants

This chapter builds on the material presented earlier in the report. The main headings and sub-headings have emerged in terms of a flow that has been influenced by the frequency of themes in the literature, especially bearing in mind grounded theory and also Granda et al's (2021) 'theories and questions by theme to ensure a gender perspective for migrants' (reproduced in Annex 2). Inevitably, there is a degree of overlap between material.

As well as reports and case studies of women and girls seeking to cross the Channel in the last few years when small boat crossings have increased, this dissertation also draws upon material from two other different but arguably the most similar situations:

- Around the period of the Calais Jungle and before (since its demolition, conditions have become even more precarious in the region);
- Small boat crossings of the Mediterranean to Europe; when these start from North Africa the trips can last several days and are much more hazardous than Channel crossings¹⁰⁴.

Schmoll (2020) points to the importance of analysis of female migration being comparative and intersectoral (e.g. by class, sexuality, ethnicity, race, physical ability and age). She also notes that, aside from the relatively rapid sea crossings in themselves, migrant journeys may last months or years. Given the desperate situation women face, many "don't have much to lose".

Finding the authentic voices of women for research is harder than for men. Articles with interviews with women are rare, largely explained by a desire to avoid exposure and self-protect. "All have in common that they live in fear of the men around them" (Kleihaurm, 2015) and, in the Jungle, women tended "to speak very little and hide their faces when they [saw] a camera" (Massaad and Paccalin (2015). Schmoll (2020) suggests they may practise *auto-invisibilisation* and UNICEF (2016) suggests some women are "strictly supervised and controlled by ... traffickers who remain at their sides day and night".

¹⁰⁴ For a recent qualitative study of different forms of violence encountered by female migrants (throughout the migration process) arriving in, or in transit through, Tunisia, see Moreno (2022).

In any case, there is detailed information available about the conditions of women and girls in Calais, with the following reports standing out in particular. Refugee Women’s Centre and Refugee Rights Europe (2019)¹⁰⁵, Richards and Timberlake (2019) and Human Rights Watch (2021) provide the most complete overviews, while Refugee Rights Europe (2016) provides the results and analysis of an extensive survey (of 870 people, including 27 women and girls) undertaken in the Calais Jungle. UNICEF (2016) also presents substantial information on the situation of boys and girls. Separately, Reehal, Taal and Maestri (2019) present accounts of asylum-seeking women’s experiences in the UK.

Annex 3 is a selection of case studies representing some of the individual experiences of women and girl migrants who have been affected by many of the issues below.

Figure 6: Documented female migrant deaths at the border of France/Belgium and the UK

Source: Maël Galisson maintains a public database of documented deaths of migrants at the border. See Annex 4 for details.

There is a clear trend of rising deaths in the last three years, at the same time as small boat crossings have increased. Since 2019, 10 deaths have been related to small boat crossings. Additionally, between 2000–2019, 10 deaths were due to suffocation hiding in trucks, and 6 due to road traffic accidents in the Calais.

¹⁰⁵ Also see <https://www.dunkirkrefugeewomenscentre.com/her-story> for a chronology of the Refugee Women’s Centre since its creation in 2015.

Women in the overall migrant population

Official statistics show that women and girls make up 1 in 10 of migrants crossing the Channel. Box 7 indicates there were very similar proportions in 2016 in both the Calais Jungle and across the central Mediterranean route. It would seem that the additional perceived and actual hazards faced by women and girls throughout their migration to get to the Channel and wait for a boat are quite dissuasive. Indeed traveling in family units is safer, and Refugee Women’s Centre and Refugee Rights Europe (2019) reported that of an estimated 300 women supported between September 2018 and September 2019, only 25 (8%) were traveling alone^{106, 107}.

The proportion may shift if migrant perceptions of the route change, as was the case for Germany in 2015–2016 when the proportion of female migration rose when the country opened its borders. Context makes an enormous difference: 90% of refugees crossing the Ukrainian border were women and children (UN Women, 2022), with very different conditions and expectations around their journey and reception.

¹⁰⁶ On 19 July 2022 when volunteering for Salam in Grande-Synthe we served lunch to about 120 people. Among them there were two women with a male partner (with two and four young boys respectively) and a group of four women, one middle-aged and three around 20-30 years old, with a young boy.

¹⁰⁷ Women traveling along reported “domestic or ‘honour’-based violence, persecution as a result of their sexual orientation or having been separated from their husbands on the migration journey”. In family units, the decision to migrate was also due to “political repression and instability, religious persecution and economic hardship” (Refugee Women’s Centre and Refugee Rights Europe, 2019)

Box 7: “Where are the women and children?”¹⁰⁸

Between January 2018 to June 2021, 12.6% of Channel migrants arriving in the UK were female (Migrant Watch UK 2022, March 9).

This proportion can be compared with a census of the Calais Jungle cited in Refugee Rights Europe (2016) in which 605 or 10.2% were female (including 400 in the Jules Ferry Centre) out of 5,900 people¹⁰⁹; a subset analysis of this population (870 individuals, of which 27 women and girls) found that “while only 30% of respondents reported that they were in Calais with their husband, some 42% said they were married, suggesting that some married women had made the journey to the camp without their spouse. Meanwhile, 47% responded that they were single.”

There is also a close parallel with the “estimated 87.5 percent of refugees and migrants who ... entered Italy via the central Mediterranean route since 2016 [who were] men and boys” (Women’s Refugee Commission, 2019).

IOM (2021) estimates the percentage of women and girls as total arrivals in Europe between 2018–2020 was approximately 20% (with a split where 7 out of 10 were women and 3 out of 10 were girls)¹¹⁰. In contrast to the upward trend of Channel crossings, the overall number of migrants arriving by sea and land in 2020 was 99,475; this was 23% less than 2019 arrivals (128,536), and 33% less than 2018 arrivals (147,683). However Frontex figures suggest a rise of 86% in the last year, the highest growth since 2016 (Gómez and Martín, 2022). The share of girls among children was less than a third, ranging considerably between the four main routes into Europe (6–38%).

By means of comparison, Donnelly and Mutiah (2018) indicate that between 2014–2020, on average women accounted for 31% of first-time asylum seekers in the EU, and in 2021, 30.4% of irregular migrant arrivals to the EU have been women and children.

¹⁰⁸ Question posed by British Future in UKHoCHAC (2022)

¹⁰⁹ Kleihauerm (2015) found an estimated 350 (5.8%) females out of 6,000 people in the Calais Jungle.

Analysis of UK home office figures between 2018 to Q2 2022 indicate that, for all asylum cases considered, during the initial decision, 58% of women were granted protection or other leave compared to 48.3% of men (see Figure 7) (UK Home Office, 2022, May 26).

The dip in Figure 7 is attributable to the first COVID lockdown. The Migrant Observatory (2022, August 22) contains a graph allowing interactive presentation of these figures by sex for 2011–2022 in the UK, suggesting male applicants aged 18–29 had a 73% success rate, 8% lower than for women the same age. The same report indicates that a much higher number of women are granted family reunion visas compared to men¹¹¹.

Figure 7: UK asylum: percentage of cases provided a grant of protection or grant of other leave (initial decision), by sex, between 2018 and Q2 2022

Source: calculated from data accessible in UK Home Office (2022, May 26)

¹¹⁰ “the share of women and of girls among children could be higher due to underreporting of these groups in official counts and statistics”

¹¹¹ While 66% of initial successful asylum decisions are granted to men, reflecting the higher proportion of male asylum seekers, only 20% of refugee family reunion visas were granted to men.

Dubow and Kushminder (2021), interviewing refugee women on their voyage to Europe, found:

“The women we interviewed did not necessarily think of their decisions as real choices. Often, they were simply trying to find the least bad option available to them. In many cases, this was not necessarily the least risky option, but rather the one that offered them some measure of control over their own lives, and some hope for a better future.”

Sexual violence

Reporting of sexual violence is widespread, and it is “an unfortunate common feature of all smuggling routes that affects female migrants in a much larger proportion than men”¹¹². It is inflicted as a form of retaliation for alleged misconduct or by lack of other means; as a form of payment, where women are coerced into sexual services in order to pay for transportation or bribes; a form of retaliation for alleged misconduct; or may “simply be a demonstration of power, misogyny, racism or sexual gratification” (UNODC, 2021).

There are often very blurred lines between sexual violence, violence, exploitation, harassment and selling sex, as the examples below show¹¹³.

Donnelly and Mutiah (2018) suggest “studies have shown that female refugees are more affected by, and more at risk of, sexual violence compared to any other population of women in the world”. Bennhold (2016) reported a Berlin centre specializing in treating traumatized female migrants where almost all of the 44 women (“some barely adults, some over 60”) had experienced sexual violence. The Women’s Refugee Commission (2019) cites two studies:

A 2015 study by Médecins du Monde (MDM) found that, out of 380 refugee and migrant men residing in eight European countries (not including Italy), 7.3 percent disclosed having experienced sexual assault, most often in the country of origin. ... Among women, 37.6% reported experiencing sexual assault; and

...

¹¹² For extensive and harrowing examples of migrant experiences in Africa up to Europe, see UNHCR and Mixed Migration Centre (2020).

¹¹³ Moreno (2022) outlines different forms of violence encountered by migrant women interviewed in Tunisia: sexual, physical, psychological and moral, economic, institutional and structural.

In [another] study conducted with migrants who had travelled along the Mediterranean route from Northern Africa to Italy, it was estimated that 90% of the women and girls who participated in the study were raped at some point during their journeys.”

The situation is echoed by the earlier PICUM (2021) report which cites Women for Refugee Women interviews in 2012 and 2013 of migrant women in detention of whom more than 85% were victims of torture or sexual violence.

Refugee girls

Donnelly and Mutiah (2018) suggest refugee girls,

“may find themselves at particular risk of SGBV¹¹⁴, given their level of dependence, their limited ability to protect themselves, and their limited participation in decision-making processes. Refugee girls are often powerless, and more easily exploited and coerced. In addition, depending on their level of development, refugee girls are unable to give informed consent, and may not even fully comprehend the sexual nature of certain behaviours.”

UNICEF (2016) cites one migrant who refused to send their older daughter on the trip to the UK, fearing rape and the dangers this would entail. Care4Calais (2022) adds:

“Many families will not risk their daughters' safety on a journey to Europe. People trafficking, sexual abuse, exploitation and violence is far more prevalent for a female travelling as a refugee, so the males of the family take on the duty, claiming asylum if they survive to bring their family over safely.”

¹¹⁴ (sexual and) “Gender-based violence [GBV] is defined as any harmful act that is perpetrated against a person’s will and based on socially ascribed differences between women and men and is rooted in deeply entrenched gender inequalities and harmful norms. Gender-based violence includes acts that inflict physical, sexual or mental harm or suffering, threats of such acts, coercion and other deprivations of liberty. It has detrimental and long-lasting consequences on the well-being, health and safety of survivors, affects their educational outcomes, and impacts on the productivity and development of countries of origin, transit and destination. It constitutes a severe human rights violation rooted in harmful gender norms and discriminatory cultural beliefs and attitudes that perpetuate inequalities between women and men.” (UN Women, 2021)

Selling sex

“People affected by conflict and crisis experience disruptions to their personal, social and economic lives, including family separation, loss of income and assets, cultural upheaval, and the collapse of traditional social structures and livelihood opportunities. Access to basic needs and livelihoods can remain interrupted for extended periods. All these factors may increase pressure on people to sell or exchange sex for money or goods to support themselves and their dependants.” (UNFPA and UNHCR, 2021)

Merkle (2021) states “sextortion is a form of corruption where instead of money or goods, a bribe is paid in the form of a sexual act ... [and] is especially prevalent at border crossings”. UNICEF (2016) interviews with Ethiopian, Eritrean and Kurdish women allowed identification of “practices involving the exchange of sexual services for the promise of passage to the UK or in order to pay for their journey and be granted access to certain areas”. While interviewing women about their experience of corruption in migrating to Europe, which can drive “prospective migrants to choose irregular, and hence riskier, migration routes”, Merkle (2021) adds that some women said they were obliged to pay a ‘double price’ of both money and sex¹¹⁵, and that in some cases “women would not only pay for their own journey in this way, but were also used as payment for entire groups of migrants”. Finnerty (2016) cites a French study suggesting African migrant women with insecure housing were eight times more likely to have transactional sex.

Richards and Timberlake (2019) note “displaced women living rough lack access to adequate support. Travelling alone, they are a target for harassment, rape and exploitation. Often, single women ‘partner’ with a man for ‘protection’, but these situations tend to go hand in hand with exploitation.” Staff working for Gynécologie Sans Frontiers also noted this practice (Welander, 2019), with “one humanitarian [speaking] of women being paired with ‘brothers’, to ‘keep them safe’, usually in exchange for sexual favours”. In one case:

“A 30-year-old Syrian mother of four fled the war with her family early last year. When her husband ran out of money to pay their smuggler in Bulgaria, he offered his wife as payment instead. For three months, she was raped almost daily to earn her family’s onward journey. Soon her own husband was abusing her, too. A “twisted logic ... “What

¹¹⁵ Merkle (2021) also cites one woman who said “As a man you always pay with your physical things, phone, money, whatever, but as a woman, the kind of corruption is different: you always pay with sex.”

her husband made her do ended up tainting his honor. She became the guilty party.”
Bennhold (2016)

Kleihauerm (2015) suggests in such environments, “if they are not protected by men, women are threatened by them”, fearing “to venture out of their tent, especially at night [due to the] danger of stalking and harassment”.

UNICEF (2016) brings many of these elements together:

“While all interviewed children say that they fear going out at night, after dark, for fear of rape, about 20 women in Calais and several Vietnamese and Iraqi Kurd women in Grande-Synthe are involved in prostitution. In an interview at the Jules Ferry Centre, a woman told us: ‘All girls receive proposals to engage in prostitution, the weakest ones accept, but if you refuse, they do not force you. Unless, of course, you owe them money.’ According to the confessions of a young Ethiopian and two young Sudanese women, they offer their services in the bars of the ‘jungle’ at night, and are paid in cash. It is with these earnings that they pay for their entries to the sites of Steenvoorde and Norrent Fontes. Young women say that ‘those who engage in prostitution pass through faster.’ There could be two forms of prostitution in which migrant women engage: the ‘reluctant but resigned’ form, practised by some women to accelerate their passage when they find themselves blocked, and the second form, which involves women exploited and abused by a trafficking network.”

(Sexual) violence affecting men and boys

“When men experience sexual violence, it is often with the intention of humiliating them. It is often used to attack their social status as a ‘man’ in various cultural and societal contexts. It may include forced witnessing of sexual violence against others (particularly family members or members of their community), genital violence attacking their reproductive capacity, or in the form of anal rape and sexual exploitation (especially when the victim is known to be from the LGBTQI+ community).” (UNODC, 2021)

There are often differences between cultures in terms of sexual violence. UNICEF (2016) mentions the Afghan practice of *Bacha bazi*, the rape of young boys, which is seen as more socially acceptable (and less likely to entail revenge) than the rape of young girls. Children explained that if this rape was conducted outside the ethnic group, retaliation between groups would take place.

Awad et al (2021), reviewing the experience of young male refugees from the Middle East, found that before and during their trip to Europe, most had been exposed to potential traumatic events “such as torture, rape, and other aversive situations associated with violence”. Studies suggest up to 97% [of all young refugees] “have had traumatic experiences, having been exposed to dangers almost without protection”.

Women’s Refugee Commission (2019) report on the Central Mediterranean Route including migrant stories from north Africa (and particularly Libya) relate particularly barbaric incidents. In north Africa:

“Men and boys are forced to witness sexual violence against women and girls (including lethal rape with objects) in official and unofficial centers of captivity and in the desert. It was also frequently reported that men and boys are forced to rape women and girls, including family members. Women are also forced to perpetrate sexual violence against refugee and migrant men and boys. Much of this violence is carried out in public or filmed for humiliation and/or extortion purposes.”

Additionally, citing testimony from the Save the Children representative in Italy in 2016,

“Fifty percent of the unaccompanied children treated by the organization’s doctors in Italy presented with a sexually transmitted infection (STI), which the medical personnel attributed to sexual exploitation during transit.”

Violence and security

41.7% of women in the Calais Jungle had experience of gender-based violence (GBV) inside the camp (Refugee Rights Europe, 2016), and:

“73% of women ‘never felt safe’ or ‘didn’t feel very safe’ in the camp – due to absence of a secure home (22%)¹¹⁶, unhealthy environment (11%), police violence (15%), fights inside the camp (11%), presence of smugglers (7.4%), unwanted male attention (3.7%), did not have legal status in France (3.7%).”

They also found “81.5% [of women] had experienced police violence since arriving in Calais (53% when attempting to journey to the UK)”, with this police violence manifested in terms of tear gas (77.8%), physical abuse (40.7%) and verbal abuse (29.6%).

Richards and Timberlake (2019) report:

“Women who face violence from their partners have little recourse to state support. When they report it, they are rarely offered safe accommodation and police hardly ever trigger a full investigation. Police have also been known to normalise abuse as “cultural”, ignoring these women’s enormous efforts to come forward and the impact that displacement has on families.

Women travelling alone regularly disappear from camps. We suspect that many are housed in private accommodation by organised networks for the purposes of sexual exploitation, forced prostitution or sex work. Single women, who generally have less money, are more likely to end up in debt bondage.

When these women have come to our attention, it is clear that there have been no meaningful follow-up or safety measures by the authorities.”

Reehal, Taal and Maestri (2019) note that asylum-seeking women in the UK “typically face a continuum of discrimination and violence” with women being “forced to choose one harm over another: whatever danger awaits them in the country of origin against the risk to them in the UK as destitute women”. They highlight the severe mental health situation for many asylum-seeking women, their possible (long-term) destitution, and inadequate state support.

¹¹⁶ Gerlach, Timberlake and Welander (2021) suggest a grave concern of the majority of women in the Calais Jungle was that they could not lock their shelter securely at night.

Health, including sexual and reproductive health

Finnerty (2016) criticized the Calais Jungle for not meeting the minimum standard (MISP) for sexual and reproductive health as set down by the inter-agency working group (IAWG) for reproductive health in humanitarian situations. She reflected that

It seemed “strange that a camp in Europe (despite its illegality) does not meet basic standards that are insisted upon in the developing world. This is an important human rights issue. The end destination for many of the people living there is the United Kingdom and clearly we may be seeing significant sexual health morbidity associated with this crisis here in the UK in the future”; and

“The potential for crisis pregnancy, acquisition and transmission of sexually transmitted infections including HIV is high and this seems to be a neglected area in the ‘jungle’ and surrounding camps.”

At the time, MSF ran an overstretched primary healthcare clinic in the Jungle, but Finnerty (2016) adds that this was “unable to provide any form of sexual health testing onsite and women [were] referred to Calais to get contraception including the morning after pill.” The hospital clinic was located nearly six kilometres from the camp, with limited information on access to services for camp inhabitants. It also had limited hours and interpreters were not always present (Richards and Timberlake, 2015), and:

“There [were] few safe spaces where women can disclose sexual health concerns or pregnancies, forcing some to travel to Brussels for terminations”; and “some hospitals have attempted to deny access to free pregnancy termination for undocumented women”.

Gynécologie Sans Frontières suggested rising abortion requests were an indication of sexual violence (Kleihauerm, 2015). Also, Refugee Rights Europe (2016) found that 56% of women had experienced health problems, and 60% did not know where to go to for healthcare and advice if pregnant.

Human Rights Watch (2021) found:

“State-provided services have failed to meet the specific needs of women. There are no separate toilets for women at Calais encampments, for example, and toilets that have been installed are not adequately lit. Practical barriers in access to water mean scarcity for everybody and pose specific challenges for women in maintaining personal hygiene during menstruation”; and

“Distance to toilets and lack of adequate lighting are safety issues for everybody and are particular concerns for women. Limited access to water and showers and the fact that menstrual hygiene products are only distributed at showers also mean that women cannot manage menstruation with dignity.”

In the UK, the Kent Public Health Observatory (2016) found that many girls had female genital mutilation, and remarks upon the vulnerability and difficulties of women who have migrated:

“Female asylum seekers are three times more likely to die in childbirth compared to the general population of the UK, and are four times more likely to experience postnatal depression.”; and

“Unfortunately, despite the legal entitlements of these women to receive maternity care, this may be misunderstood by healthcare providers, particularly in relation to women whose applications for asylum has been refused. Commissioners of maternity services must ensure providers are aware of the rights of these women, and of their legal obligation to provide maternity care.”

Neal (2022) also suggests potential gaps in UK Home Office staff receiving migrants who did not systematically ask women about pregnancy.

Pregnancy, children and dependants

Dubox and Kushminder (2021) interviewed 28 Afghan, Eritrean and Syrian women during their journeys to Europe. They found:

“Many of the women we interviewed were traveling with small children, were pregnant, or had given birth at some point on their journey. Pregnancy and motherhood had a significant impact on their migration experience, by shaping their decisions about when to migrate, whether to take their children with them, and which countries to stay in or move onwards from.” Additionally,

“On one hand, being pregnant increases the risks and difficulty of the route. On the other, women – especially if pregnant or traveling with young children – were sometimes spared some of the abuse and exploitation that their male counterparts suffered as the kidnappers and smugglers took mercy on them as mothers.”

Gerlach, Timberlake and Welander (2021) cite one woman in the Calais Jungle saying that she miscarried due to the effects of tear gas with another saying she “had given birth in the back of a truck”. The death of Aleksandra Hazhar occurred three days after being born prematurely following the interception by French border police of her mother Rupa Sharif while she attempted to take a small boat on 1–2 September 2020.

Kleihauerm (2015) suggests “some women even get pregnant with the purpose of being less likely to be harassed or sexually assaulted”.

Richards and Timberlake (2015) found in the Jungle:

“Childcare, especially for new-borns, [was] difficult with limited access to clean water and washing facilities. Illness and infection are passed on quickly including scabies, head lice and impetigo.” and

“children living rough are at risk of sexual and economic exploitation, especially when unaccompanied or with a single parent.”

Maya, a volunteer at the Calais Jungle with Auberge des Migrants, observed “Most [women] are not as quick as men, and often they have a child in tow, so they cannot get into a truck without men’s help.” (Graham-Harrison, 2015).

Water, food, shelter and education

Generally speaking, the makeshift shelters in the Calaisis have little to no access to clean running water, showers or toilets. There are rarely locks.

In the Calais Jungle, Finnerty (2016) remarked that there was “inadequate lighting, toilet and washing facilities”. Refugee Rights Europe (2016) added that there were:

“too few bathrooms, which are often not secure and used by both men and women ... [these] facilities risk becoming dangerous spaces, where women and girls may be at risk of sexual violence or harassment. As a result, women residing in refugee camps may avoid food or drink so that they don’t have to use bathrooms at night, when they would be most at risk of such violations”

Human Rights Watch (2021) found:

“State-provided food distributions did not include milk or other food suitable for young children or for women who are pregnant or breastfeeding, we heard”

“It’s been one month since I showered,” a woman staying in Grande-Synthe told Human Rights Watch in December 2020. ‘It is difficult for my children, it’s difficult being clean, eating, washing, playing,’ she added.”

“For women with young children, collection of water poses particular challenges. “Men have more access to water because they are more mobile. Women may have to stay in the woods with their children. They need more water, but they may have to depend on men to get water for them,” said Clémentine Le Berre of the PSM [Plateforme des Soutiens aux Migrant.e.s].”

In the Calais Jungle, Refugee Rights Europe (2016) found that 92.3% of women did not have the chance to access education or information on rights and opportunities, compared to 77.3%–79.3% for the camp’s general population.

State assistance

Human Rights Watch (2021) add:

“in Grande-Synthe, an accommodation center to which families were frequently sent had “no hot water, no food for children, no social worker, no real way for people who do not speak English or French to get information on asylum. It’s really far from the city, with no public transport available. Women will tell us, ‘We cannot take the bus to go to the supermarket to buy nappies or food for our babies.’ ‘They feel better in the forest, where the supermarket is nearby,’ said Laure Pichot, then the Utopia 56 coordinator in Grande-Synthe, in November 2020.

...

Adults, including families with children, request access to emergency accommodation by calling a dedicated number, 115. In practice, when groups call 115 on behalf of single adult migrants, they often receive the response that shelters are full. ‘When we call to arrange emergency shelter for the women we encounter, very often the response is that they cannot get it,’ Juliette Delaplace [of Secours Catholique] said.

...

Families and single adults who have already stayed in emergency accommodation cannot stay a second time. ... an Eritrean woman was denied emergency shelter in early November 2020. “She needs psychological support. She can’t be accommodated at the emergency shelter offered by the 115 because she has already benefited from them. In Calais, the 115 shelter for women and families is limited to two to four nights. After that time, the only option is the CAES¹¹⁷,’ Juliette Delaplace said, referring to the reception centers. ‘We gave her a tent and blankets,’ she told us, adding that this case was not unusual.

...

In Calais, after three nights, migrant women are told to go to the CAES. If they say no, authorities can deny them 115 accommodation. That contrasts with how they handle cases of French women who are homeless. They have access to emergency shelter with no three-day time limit,’ Delaplace said. Authorities in the department of Nord take the same approach, Utopia 56 told us.

¹¹⁷ Centre d’Accueil et d’Examen des Situations (see <https://vieactive.fr/etablissements/caes/>). Migrants tend to see this as a last resort, fearful that they will be sent back to the first country in which they entered Europe due to the Dublin Protocol.

Border crossings

UNODC (2021) found that:

“Women run a significantly higher risk of experiencing health dangers in [crossing borders] as they are performing tasks like childcare or breastfeeding while in transit;

...

A percentage of women engage in the journey while being pregnant and are therefore subject to reduced mobility and an increased risk of dehydration;

...

Findings also indicate that women tend to have weaker swimming skills, which is compounded by the fact that they often wear longer and heavier clothes than men, making it harder for them to float.

...

women’s position on the boats is determined by misconceptions that unintentionally endanger them more. In the Central Mediterranean, women are often placed in the middle of the rubber boat, where they are thought to be more protected as they are as far as possible from the water. However, it is in the middle of the boat that seawater and fuel mix up, creating a toxic substance that burns people’s skin and often causes them severe injuries. There they are also more at risk of being stepped on and suffocated when the boat is in distress.”

With Neal (2022) observing of arriving Channel migrants:

“Fuel burns, a chemical burn which occurs when petrol mixes with seawater and comes into contact with the skin, were the most common injury“

Contrasting with the view of some that “women are ... hysterical and not [to be] taken seriously” (Schmoll, 2020), UNODC (2021) note that during crises:

“First-hand accounts report that in the middle of situations of panic on board, more than once women emerged as the best point of contact, as they managed to stay calm, listen carefully to understand how to find the GPS coordinates on the phone and speak clearly to provide precious information.

However when searching for missing or dead migrant relatives,

“Women do often not receive relevant information that could help them to locate loved ones due to gender stereotypes that portray women as overly emotional. They are excluded from decision-making processes in an attempt to ‘reduce their suffering’ which often leads to women’s perspectives being dismissed. They are often denied access to social spaces that would help them in their rescue mission and are often disproportionately impacted by financial costs linked to search and repatriation operations.”

Solidarity

In such conditions. Richards and Timberlake (2019) remark:

“Women, in particular, show fierce solidarity in caring and providing for each other. Hope and a desire for stability continue to hold strong in the face of exhaustion and daily rights violations for displaced people on the northern French coastline.”

Welander (2019) cites Gynécologie Sans Frontières who observed:

“the majority of women, in the makeshift camps and forests, survive by forming friendship groups, often based around shared language or nationality.”

Analysis

The dissertation has already considered, especially from a gender perspective, how migration and discourse around it can be affected by stereotypes, and how various pull and push factors influence migrant decisions.

In a very crude way, by considering word counts of 'women', it is possible to compare the major UK and French parliamentary reports. 'Women' appear on 2 (3%) of the 59 pages of UKHoCHAC (2012) and 'femme(s)' in 56 (12%) of the 453 pages (including annexes) of Krimi and Nadot (2021). However the percentages are higher for the two reports by independent UK Inspector reports (13% for Neal (2020) and 20% for Independent Chief Inspector of Borders and Immigration, UK Government (2021) compared to the French Défenseur des droits (2018) with 9.2%.

It seems difficult to draw many conclusions from these differences, although the documents can be considered to be gender-sensitive and also gender-specific given they provide certain recommendations. Conversely, the research found that the majority of media reporting did not mention gender at all, which in part can be attributed to limited time and space but also (for women and even more so for LGBTQI+ people) could be argued to be gender-biased, i.e. 'active exclusion' which 'produces negative impacts on certain genders'.

Nevertheless there were a good number of gender-sensitive reports and stories (which nevertheless required extensive research to unearth) as demonstrated in the case studies in Annex 3. But it was difficult to clearly identify situations which were truly gender-responsive, i.e. 'responding to specific needs of migrants by gender' *and* 'addressing the structural causes of gender discrimination in migration [which] transforms systems, norms, policies or structures'. Even the temporary existence of the Jules Ferry Centre or the ongoing active involvement of organizations dedicated to women's issues in the field, such as the Refugee Women's Centre¹¹⁸, may be operationally and sensitively meeting the needs of female migrants (and largely meeting Gender with Age Marker elements), but face entrenched structural barriers which perpetuate the situation.

¹¹⁸ the mission statement includes "advocating for the effective implementation of a policy of reception and dignified housing and support all awareness-raising actions that promote integration." (Refugee Women's Centre, 2021)

Overall, there is a big difference between ample and detailed normative guidelines on gender compared with substantive mentions of gender in operational documents. On one hand this suggests there is a need to continue (promoting an) understanding of gender differences and their nuances, and appreciation of the differential impacts they may lead to. On the other it should also be recognized that gender is only one among many factors influencing everyday life. However, gender intersects with many varying elements, in changing contexts, and appreciating this allows a better appreciation of vulnerabilities, bias and decision-making. As has been said anonymously, “When you’re accustomed to privilege, equality feels like oppression”.

Conclusions

The situation of migrants undertaking Channel crossings is extremely concerning, particularly for more vulnerable women and girls, and is exacerbated for those with limited resources. A 'hostile climate' towards migrants exists in both the UK and France. There are atrocious conditions documented on both sides of the Channel, but in particular in northern France where most migrants find themselves excluded and repeatedly harassed, and unable to find stable shelter or other basic necessities. There are many cases of inadequate, or indeed non-existent, state protection, worse than in many refugee camps in the developing world.

Public perceptions are influenced by stereotypes, and opinions are divided on the question of migration but, in all places where migrants arrive, there tend to be a minority of people from the host country who will either go out of their way to support or oppose them. The vast majority of people tend to be apathetic.

Yet people will keep on migrating, as demonstrated by clear push and pull factors, and there is every indication in this unstable world that numbers of people seeking a better life in wealthier countries will increase (e.g. see figure 8). In 2022, despite considerable opposition, the UK government is currently playing up the deterrent factor of sending migrants to Rwanda which raises similar issues compared to Australia's Operation Sovereign Borders. This might reduce but not eliminate irregular migration for various reasons – e.g. given the relatively short boat passage across the Channel, the impossibility of having full policing coverage at either coast, and apparent abundant opportunities in the UK informal economy. A cynical observer in the UK might even suggest that some elements – the continued media profile and stereotyping (particularly in terms of threatening male migrants), the idea mooted by some politicians to withdraw the UK European Court of Human Rights “to take back control” again, the neglect of UK Home Office asylum procedures and reception, and criticisms of the French – point to efforts to increase the salience of and fears about immigration for political leverage. Others would also argue that increasing budgets for border operations and security are exploited for profitability by a few ahead of protection for many.

Figure 8: Areas becoming uninhabitable due to climate change between the present day and what is projected in 2100, principally due to heat and water stress

Source: Berliner Morgenpost (2022)

There are already a number of existing and detailed recommendations that are worth highlighting: for migrants in Europe (IOM 2021, p.4, focusing on women); the situation in France (Défenseur de droits, 2018, pp.70–75; the multiple recommendations¹¹⁹ of Krimi and Nadot, 2021); and to all stakeholders to address the precarious state of many migrants in northern France (Human Rights Watch, 2021, pp.10–14).

Repeated recommendations from many sources point to the need for managed migration as the solution (or even solving the ‘push’ factors such as wars and inequality in originating countries, albeit with an altogether different magnitude). In any case migration, and the situation, is a classic ‘wicked problem’ requiring a political solution, although when politics is based on polarization rather than consensus there will always be unnecessary division. On one hand, in circumstances quite different to the UK, it is possible to look at Germany which has integrated around a million migrants since 2015¹²⁰, in a much more structured way than many other countries. Also, to be fair, it should not be forgotten that the UK has also set quotas to receive

¹¹⁹ Especially recommendations 13, 15 and 22.

¹²⁰ Much has been written about this. For example see Esposito (2022) on integrating refugee women into Germany.

refugees from Afghanistan and Ukraine which is also managing migration. The problem is that any country will draw a limit at some point and, even if the UK processed asylum applications in France or elsewhere outside its national borders, there will always be more applicants than places. Nevertheless, the UK and French governments have an implicit and explicit policy of dissuasion, and will continue to maintain this, albeit arguably with plenty of scope for improvement of coordination.

Which leads to the main recommendation of this report: ***that coordination and understanding between the UK and France on irregular migration needs to improve, ensuring all stakeholders (particularly migrants themselves¹²¹) are able to contribute.*** There are many cases of cross-national communication difficulties between the two countries, and it is not clear whether (public) multi-stakeholder cross-national consultations have taken place on the issue¹²². If these took place, they would need to be backed up by political commitment to act on recommendations. There is an interest for all sides in building on such consultations to move forward to help track a clearer way forward.

¹²¹ Apart from the example of Zainab (Spratt, 2021), research for the dissertation found no references to migrants who had crossed in a small boat and then settled in the UK. It could be instructive to learn from their experiences.

¹²² Although UKHoCHAC (2022) included submissions from the Mayor of Calais and President of Hauts-de-France, which may offer something to build upon

Annex 1: Charts showing UK public opinion on immigration and Channel crossings

Saliency of immigration in the UK, 1994-2019

Note and source: Ipsos MORI data. Until January 2015, 'immigration' included responses of 'race relations'. After this point, 'immigration' became its own category. Data for 'immigration' are actual percentages. The other categories report six-month rolling averages.

Source: The Migrant Observatory (2020)

Immigration / Immigrants

What do you see as the most/other important issues facing Britain today?

Base: representative sample of c.1,000 British adults age 18+ each month, interviewed face-to-face in home
N.B. April 2020 data onwards is collected by telephone; previous months are face-to-face

Source: Ipsos Issues Index

Source: IPSOS (2022, July)

Half of those dissatisfied with the Government's handling of immigration cite not enough being done to stop channel crossings.

Q And for which of the following reasons, if any, make you dissatisfied with the way the current government is dealing with immigration?

Base: All respondents dissatisfied with the way the Government's dealing with immigration (W13: 1932); Fieldwork dates: 28 January to 10 February 2022

Source: IPSOS (2022, July)

A majority continue to have sympathy for migrants attempting to cross the English Channel.

Q How much sympathy if at all, if any, do you have for the migrants attempting to cross the English Channel by boat to come to Britain?

NB: Fieldwork conducted prior to invasion of Ukraine

Base: All respondents (W9: 2006; W11: 2532; W12: 4000; W13: 3206); Fieldwork dates: 28 January to 10 February 2022

Source: IPSOS (2022, July)

A quarter of Britons say the French government's handling of the issue is the main reason for the increase in asylum seekers attempting to cross the Channel

From what you have seen or heard, what do you think is the main reason for the recent increase in the number of migrants attempting to cross the English Channel by boat? %

YouGov

24-25 November 2021

Source: Kirk (2021)

Annex 2: Key gender frameworks and tools to facilitate analysis

1. Gender with Age Marker

<https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/system/files/iasc-gam-information-sheet.pdf>

The GAM assesses projects for 12 essential programme elements known as Gender Equality Measures or GEMs.

The GAM tracks whether basic programme actions are in place. Good programming requires that affected people participate in and influence all stages of a project.

Programmes should logically flow from the gendered needs analysis, to tailoring or adapting activities in response to analysis, through to who benefits from the intervention. GAM coding reflects the presence and consistency of these actions, as well as the integration of gender and age within them.

2. Levels of gender responsiveness

Adapted from <https://gendermigrationhub.org/> and <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559709/table/ch2.t1/>

Gender-responsive

Responds to specific needs of all migrants; addresses the structural causes of gender discrimination in migration and transforms systems, norms, policies or structures

Gender-Specific

Focuses on genders of all migrants; addresses some gender inequalities but not structural inequities

Gender-Sensitive

Acknowledges but does not address gender inequalities; “in words only”

Gender-Blind

Appears unbiased, but reinforces gender inequalities; produces uneven outcomes for different genders.

Gender-Biased

Actively discriminates or excludes; produces negative impacts on certain genders (typically women or LGBTQI+) of migrants

3. Dimensions, indicators and key questions to consider when analyzing migration narratives from a gender perspective (Güell and Parella, 2021)

- Boundary-making – us/them; link to ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation; explicit or explicit
- Narratives' success – how dominant; what stereotypes; how are migrant women portrayed?; with agency?; which issues (reproductive/productive); family or market role
- Narrative production in social media
- Narrative production in the public debate
- Impact on individual attitudes and beliefs
- Impact of narratives on migrants' decisions (to migrate, men and women)
- Impact of narratives on national policy-making (Migrant women participate? Who do decisions mainly affect?)
- Impact of narratives on EU policy-making
- Coproduction of narratives?

4. Reasons behind women's migration (reproduced from Boyd and Grieco, 2003)

“A United Nations report on women and migration argues that the impact of women's status and roles on their propensity to migrate must be considered at three levels: individual, familial, and societal.

- Individual factors include age, birth order, race/ethnicity, urban/rural origins, marital status (single, married, divorced, widowed), reproductive status (children or no children), role in the family (wife, daughter, mother), position in family (authoritative or subordinate), educational status, occupational skills/training, labor force experience, and class position.

- Family factors include size, age/sex composition, life-cycle stage, structure (nuclear, extended, etc.), status (single parent, both parents, etc.), and class standing.
- Societal factors include those community norms and cultural values that determine whether or not women can migrate and, if they can, how (i.e., labor or family reunification) and with whom (alone or with family).

Certain macro characteristics of the country of origin can also influence gender-specific migration propensities. These characteristics can interact with the gender relations and the position of women in the sending society and affect decisions about who moves and when. These characteristics include: the state of the economy (agrarian, industrial, level of development); the types of economies present within various communities (i.e., all developed, mixed agrarian/industrial, some subsistence horticulturalists); the level of displacement caused by economic changes and shifts in production technologies; land tenure laws; labor market conditions and conditions of work (wage levels, benefits); the ability of the economy to provide jobs and the type of jobs available (number of industries); the ability of the national government to provide related infrastructure (education, job training); the geographic location of the country and the language(s) of the sending society; the relation and integration of the national economy into the world economy; the supply and demand conditions for the factors of production in sending and related receiving communities; and the presence or absence of established migration systems with other areas.”

5. Themes and questions by theme to ensure a gender perspective for migrants (Granda et al, 2021)

Temas y preguntas tipo para garantizar la incorporación de la perspectiva de género en las políticas de atención a migrantes

TEMA	PREGUNTA TIPO
Albergue, artículos no alimenticios y transporte humanitario	¿Están diseñados los albergues para permitir la privacidad y la seguridad con dignidad? ¿Tienen las mujeres, niñas, hombres y niños acceso a espacios seguros?
Seguridad alimentaria	¿Cuáles son las tendencias de consumo? ¿Cómo usan las mujeres y los hombres sus ingresos?
Salud	¿Se dispone de servicios de salud sexual y reproductiva, y se hace un manejo apropiado de los casos de violencia de género?
Nutrición	¿Cómo afecta la crisis el bienestar nutricional de mujeres, niñas, hombres y niños? ¿Quién tiene mayores riesgos de desnutrición y afectación de su salud?
Acceso a agua	¿Algún grupo se enfrenta a barreras y riesgos de protección en relación con el agua y el aseo?
Educación	Cuántos menores se encuentran por fuera de la escuela? ¿Cómo afectan el género y la edad el acceso a la educación?
Protección	¿Cuáles son los distintos riesgos de protección que la crisis ha causado o agudizado? (Ej., documentos de identidad expirados, violencia sexual, trabajo infantil, matrimonio temprano, trata de personas).
Integración y medios de vida	¿Quiénes (mujeres, hombres, niñas y niños) participan en el trabajo de cuidado no remunerado? ¿Qué funciones y responsabilidades tienen?
Iniciativas basadas en efectivo	¿Qué apoyo adicional (para el cuidado de niños y el tránsito) necesitan las mujeres para participar en actividades laborales?

Annex 3: Indicative case studies of women and girl migrants

Aleksandra Hazhar and Rupak Sharif

Rupak Sharif, an Irakian Kurd, was 35 weeks' pregnant and part of a group of 18 Iraqis attempting to cross the Channel on the night of 1–2 September 2020. The group was apprehended by a border control and, according to her family, the intervention led to her waters breaking and Rupak experiencing extreme pain. She was kept immobile in the cold for three hours before the border control left without providing assistance. It was only with the help of her family and a second border control that she was taken to hospital in Calais, where she gave birth to Aleksandra Hazhar. However, Aleksandra had various neurological and respiratory complications at birth and died three days later on 5 September 2020.

Passeurs d'hospitalités ~ des exilés à Calais. (2021, April 2021). Justice pour la famille d'Aleksandra. <https://passeursdhospitalites.wordpress.com/2021/04/28/justice-pour-la-famille-daleksandra/>

also <https://www.leparisien.fr/faits-divers/a-calais-un-hommage-organise-en-memoire-du-bebe-mort-dune-migrante-05-09-2021-6LTADR4RWRBVVCOEPTI5RLI6W4.php>

Hannah

In the Calais Jungle, Hannah, a 24-year-old Syrian who was five months' pregnant, slept in the main camp as there were no places in the Womens' Centre. Each night she walked two miles to try to sneak onto lorries and trains.

Graham-Harrison, E. (2015, July 31). Women in Calais camps: 'I have to focus on how I can stay alive'. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/jul/31/women-in-calais-camps-i-have-to-focus-on-how-i-can-stay-alive>

Julienne

Chapter One (pp.33–56) of Schmoll's book is dedicated to the story of Julienne, in which she relates her life between 2016–2019, having left Cameroon to arrive in France (including time in Montpellier, Caen and Paris) via Libya and Sicily. The story explores the key themes addressed later in the book (see p.46 of this dissertation) *Schmoll, C. (2020), Les damnées de la mer : Femmes et frontières en Méditerranée, France, Cahiers Libres La Découverte.*

Kiana

“I would like to have a peaceful life. I would like to go back to school, do more studying and meet new friends. I would really like to know what will happen tomorrow. I am sad because I am in a situation where I don’t know if I will be able to go on studying. I will never be able to see my family again or go back to my country. But I am glad to be here in safety and I hope to have more beautiful days.”

La Plateforme des Soutiens aux Migrant.e.s (2019). Women crossing borders / Femmes traversant les frontières | Journal des Jungles No. 13. http://www.psmigrants.org/site/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/JDJ_13_WEB.pdf

This is one of eight short testimonies of women who passed through the Calais Jungle.

Mervat Jalabi

Mervat, a 53-year-old Syrian, accompanied by Mohammed, her 55-year-old husband. They had left their three-bedroom house in a middle class suburb in Aleppo four months earlier. Their adult children managed to reach the UK and Sweden in 2014. Despite the couple initially not wishing to leave, a bomb destroyed their house, forcing them to flee the country. Mervat’s daughter Mai, 26, was living in Huddersfield and had just had her first child. Mervat said, "I'm worried that I'm not there and that she's scared," she says. "She needs her mother and I can't help her."

Callaghan, L. (2015, December 21). Inside The Calais ‘Jungle’ Camp – What Refugee Women Take With Them. <https://www.refinery29.com/en-us/2015/12/99936/calais-refugee-photo-story-crisis>

Also contains studies of Houda, Mahoba, Narges, Shermin and Tamina.

Milad

Milad, a 22-year-old Syrian, was with her uncle in the Calais Jungle, staying for most of her time in her tent “surrounded by men”, spending “her days listening to the world outside: wind thrashing against the tents, football games in the day and occasional fights at night.”

Massaad, T. and Paccalin, C. (2015, September 14). 'I'm surrounded by men': Life for women in the Calais ‘Jungle’, <https://www.france24.com/en/20150914-women-migrants-calais-jungle-plaint> with a video report.

Ruth

Ruth is a 14-year-old from Eritrea. Faced with the choice of either joining the military or being a child bride, she chose to leave home. After many trials and tribulations, she succeeded in traveling unaccompanied across Africa and Europe to the UK, finally boarding a lorry from France to the UK.

BBC. (2016, July 8). Ruth's story: One child refugee's journey from Eritrea to England.

<https://www.bbc.co.uk/newsround/36714334> (animated text and video)

Winta

Winta left Ethiopia aged 13 in order to escape from an arranged marriage with a much older man. She stayed in Sudan for three years to pay back what she owed and pay for the next stage of her journey. She was regularly raped in Libya and forced into prostitution on a number of occasions in order to earn money more quickly. Eventually she succeeded in crossing Europe and, after reaching the UK, filed a request for asylum.

UNICEF France, UNICEF UK and Fondation EDF. (2016, June). Neither safe nor sound: Unaccompanied children on the coastline of the English Channel and the North Sea.

https://www.unicef.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Unicef_NeitherSafeNorSound.pdf Also contains case studies of Martha and Yohanna.

Zainab Sadat Hossaini

An Afghan aged 17, Zainab crossed the Channel on Christmas Day 2018. She relates her trip which was via Tehran and Lesbos. Now in Kent she is training to be a pilot.

Spratt, V. (2021, December 2). A Young Woman Refugee On What It's Actually Like To Cross The Channel. <https://www.refinery29.com/en-gb/2021/12/10784740/migrant-refugee-crossing-english-channel>

Eight experts came together from the World Universities Network to work on a project looking into women, migration and their stories of resilience. Between them they interviewed approximately 150 women and are publishing their stories in a collaborative storytelling project (two collations below).

Kuschminder, K. (2021, November 21). We interviewed 150 women migrants – revealing how their journeys involve peril at every turn. <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/we-interviewed-150-women-migrants-revealing-how-their-journeys-involve-peril-every-turn>

Refugee women's journeys to Europe

“a third of those who cross the Mediterranean to seek asylum are women – these are their stories.”

Dubow, T. and Kushminder, K. (2021, November 25). *'I don't have any other choice' – refugee women's journeys to Europe.* <https://womenandmigration.com/case-study/journey/>

Women's experiences of corruption while migrating to Europe

“Many irregular migrants to the European Union are driven out of their country of origin by corruption that makes daily life a struggle. But that corruption follows them en route in the form of bribery, violence and sextortion.”

Merkle, O. (2021, November 25). *'I never knew the journey was that risky' – women's experiences of corruption while migrating to Europe.* <https://womenandmigration.com/case-study/corruption/>

Annex 4: Details of recorded deaths of women and girls at the France/Belgium/UK border from 1999 to 9/8/2022

Data comes from the database of Maël Galisson documenting deaths at these borders from 1999, reported in *Institute of Race Relations. (2020). Deadly crossings and the militarisation of Britain's borders.* <https://irr.org.uk/article/deadly-crossings/>

“The up-to-date database is shown in map form (<https://neocarto.github.io/calais/en/>) and a timeline (<https://www.tiki-toki.com/timeline/entry/1519092/Deaths-at-border-FranceBelgiumUK/>).”

The document explains:

“The importance of counting and accounting for deaths at the border was recognised by Leanne Weber and Sharon Pickering, who in their 2011 book *Globalisation and borders: death at the global frontier* insisted on the importance of first, finding out as much as possible about the lives of those who died seeking safety, security, family or a better life, to re-humanise the people behind the statistics; and second, showing that the deaths are not ‘natural’ or ‘tragic accidents’ but man-made, created by policies which do not merely close borders but also erect ever more obstacles to safe travel for the most vulnerable. The work of Maël Galisson is in this tradition.”

As 9 August 2022, a total of 351 total deaths had been recorded. The 30 female deaths represent 8.7% of the total (excluding 8 people for whom the gender was not reported).

Details for each of the female deaths are reported below. The database provides links to original sources with more details.

9/4/2000

A woman died in hospital after falling under the wheels of a truck in St Leonard's, Hastings. The other four people hidden in the truck were arrested.

8/12/2001 – 2

Thirteen people (11 Turkish, 1 Algerian and 1 Albanian) trying to reach Dover following directions from a smuggler hid in a container at the port of Zeebrugge (Belgium). This container was unfortunately not destined for Dover, but for the south of Ireland. They remained locked in this grave-like container for 4 days. When they were discovered in Wexford, 8 of them – Mustafa Demir (23), Yuksel Ucaroglu (26), Hasan Kalendragil, Kalender Kalendragil (15), Zeliha Kalendragil (10), Samiye Guler (28), Imam Guler (9) and Berkam Guler (4) – were dead. The survivors were all in a critical condition, dehydrated and in a semi-coma.

12/7/2003

Elmas Ozmico, a 40-year-old Kurdish woman, died of sepsis. She had developed an abscess on her way from Turkey to join her husband, hiding in a truck with her two children, aged 8 and

7, and her nephew, aged 19. Upon their arrival in Dover on 8 July, her nephew Emurallah Sanci asked for her to be examined by a doctor, but his request was ignored. She was transferred to hospital the next day, after losing consciousness, nineteen hours after arriving and requesting assistance. At the inquest, medical experts said Elmas Ozmico could have survived if she had received prompt medical care.

7/7/2007

Louam Beyene, a 19-year-old Eritrean woman, died after being hit by a car while she was running across the A16 motorway in Calais to escape the police. Her body was repatriated to Eritrea.

17/2/2009

Glara. An Iraqi Kurdish woman who lived in the camp set up in the Grande-Synthe area, on the A16 motorway, near Dunkerque, gave birth prematurely. The child, named Glara, did not survive. A funeral fundraiser was organised by the Movement Against Racism and for Friendship between Peoples (MRAP) of Dunkerque. Glara is buried in the Muslim burial area of the Grande-Synthe cemetery.

13/8/2012

An unidentified Vietnamese woman of about 35 was found dead on the beach of Wimereux, in a diving suit. It seems she wanted to swim across the Channel.

26/10/2014

Sara, 16 or 26, from Ethiopia, died after being hit by a car at night on the A16 motorway near Calais.

29/6/2015

The body of 23-year-old Eritrean Zebiba Ali Saïd was found on the A16 motorway between Calais and Marck after being hit by a vehicle. She was traveling with two friends trying to reach England.

24/7/2015

Ghebrensae Ganet, a 23-year-old Eritrean woman, died after being hit by a car on the A16 motorway at Calais, near the Eurotunnel.

12/7/2016

Fisehatisation Samrawit, a 19-year-old from Eritrea, died after being hit by a lorry on the Calais port ring road. She arrived in Calais 5 weeks earlier, alone, trying to join her older brother in Britain. She rested for a few days in the Jules Ferry women's accommodation centre, then left for the Steenvoorde camp to try to cross the border. When this camp was suddenly dismantled by police, she returned, like many others, to Calais. The following day a lorry hit her as she tried desperately to stop traffic to find a way to cross.

6/5/2018

Mawda, a 2-year-old Kurdish girl, was shot dead by a Belgian police officer on the A24, near Mons, Belgium during a car chase. Mawda was traveling with her parents and other migrants in the back of a van when police opened fire in order to stop the vehicle. A bullet penetrated Mawda's cheek and she died.

9/8/2019

Mitra Mehrad drowned in the Channel whilst trying to reach the UK aboard a dinghy with 19 others. Rescue teams were sent to assist the dinghy in distress. Her body has not yet been recovered.

23/10/2019 – 8

39 people were found dead in the back of a refrigerated truck in Waterglade Industrial Park in Grays, Essex (GB). The victims, 8 women and 31 men, were all originally from north east Vietnam and died of suffocation during their attempt to cross the border hidden in the truck.

5/9/2020

Aleksandra Hazhar. Daughter of Hazhar Ibrahim and Rupak Sharif. Born 2/9/20, died 5/9/20 of perinatal anoxia following a premature birth. Her family, the mother heavily pregnant, were intercepted on a beach by the police following an attempted boat crossing. They were shocked, soaked and cold and, despite calls for help, were made to wait for over five hours before being released and being able to go to hospital. No medical care was received before that. An emergency birth was carried out, but despite doctors' efforts the baby did not survive. The parents have since filed a legal complaint, and the mother wrote a letter. They wish for it to be heard, hence, here it is for you to read.

27/10/2020 – 2

On Tuesday 27 October 2020, seven people died trying to cross the North Sea aboard a boat. Shortly after departure, the boat, which was carrying at least 18 people, was wrecked off Loon-Plage. Among the recorded victims is a family from Iranian Kurdistan (a couple, Rasul Iran Nezhad and Shiva Mohammad Panahi, and their three children, Anita, Armin and Artin).

24/11/2021 – 6

Twenty-seven people were found dead [when a small boat crossing the Channel sank], while two others survived and were rescued, and another is still missing. Sixteen of the victims were identified as Kurdish people from Iraqi Kurdistan, including ten men, four women and two children [including "a young girl"]; four more were Afghan men, three Ethiopians, one Kurdish man from Iran, a Somali woman, one Vietnamese man, and an Egyptian man

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